

**Monodrama and Music Theatre as Transformative
Artistic Experiences. From a Performative to an
Embodied Acting Musician/Guitarist.**

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A thesis submitted in total fulfilment of the requirements of
the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
January 2018

Melbourne Conservatorium of Music
The University of Melbourne

Abstract

This practice-based thesis investigates the changing role of a musician (a guitarist, and his instrument) from that of an accompanist to a protagonist in a body of works in the genres of Monodrama and Music Theatre. The folio of performances (and the works performed) has been curated to clearly trace the guitarist's trajectory from an instrumentalist to a fully embodied acting musician. The works, their collaborative creation and performances are explored in an exegetic dissertation. The first part of the folio and this dissertation consists of a traditional melodrama for narrator and guitar by Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco, followed by a recent work by Alexander Schubert and my transcription of *Fidélité* for female harpist by Georges Aperghis, the latter two of which require the engagement of a Performative Acting Musician. The second part presents and analyses five case studies of Monodramas/Melodramas by Arturo Corrales, James Rushford, Erick Bongcam, David Chisholm and Daniel Zea that explore issues of isolation, illness, trauma and hysteria. These works draw upon early twentieth-century monodramatic traditions that explore an individual's sense of alienation, and call for the participation of an Embodied Acting Musician. All the works presented in Part two have been premiered during the timeframe of this PhD.

The folio of performances is presented in the form of live recordings of the compositions discussed throughout the dissertation. It also contains two appendices, the first of which offers notes towards a performance edition of the first quire of Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco's *Platero y yo*, op. 190 for narrator and guitar. The second appendix comprises my adaptation of Georges Aperghis' *Fidélité pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme*.

Declaration

This is to certify that

1. the thesis comprises only my original work towards the Doctor of Philosophy except where indicated;
2. due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used;

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, enclosed within a hand-drawn oval. The signature appears to be 'M. Carrasco'.

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Date: January 15, 2018.

Acknowledgements

I would firstly like to thank my principal supervisor, Dr. Michael Christoforidis, who has encouraged rigorous thinking and provided unwavering support of my intentions with this research. Secondly, I would like to thank my associate supervisors Dr. Ken Murray and Dr. Elliott Gyger for their support.

I would like to thank the Melbourne Conservatorium of Music, the University of Melbourne, for providing a wonderfully supportive environment for me during my studies. I also gratefully acknowledge the generosity of the Chilean Government in providing me with a PhD scholarship Beca Chile and the Australian Government in providing me with an Australian Postgraduate Award. This enabled me to commit myself fully to my endeavours at the University.

Finally, I would like to thank all the living composers, musicians and collaborative artists that made possible this interdisciplinary research.

A. Folio of Performances (constituting 75% of overall PhD thesis)

1) ***Platero y yo, op. 190*** (1960) by Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco [video]

Sapidah Kian: narrator

Mauricio Carrasco: guitar

Recorded live at the Guitar Perspectives concert, 17/08/2015, University of Melbourne, Australia.

2) ***Sensate Focus*** (2014) by Alexander Schubert [video]

Ensemble Vortex.

Mauricio Carrasco: guitar

Anne Gillot: bass clarinet

Florian Feyer: percussion

Patrick Schleuter: violin

Daniel Zea: live electronics

Recorded live at the Ensemble Vortex Concert Season, 05/02/2016, Théâtre Cité Bleue, Geneva, Switzerland.

3) ***Fidélité/In-Fidelity*** (1983) by Georges Aperghis, adapted by Mauricio Carrasco [video]

Jude Anderson: director

Sapidah Kian: actress

Mauricio Carrasco: guitar/voice

Recorded live at the Festival of Live Arts, 12/03/2016, Arts House, Melbourne, Australia.

4) ***BUG Trilogy*** (2014) by Arturo Corrales [video]

Christophe Bergon: mise-en-scène

Ensemble Vortex.

Mauricio Carrasco: guitar

Rada Hadjikota-Schleuter: violin

Jocelyne Rudasigwa: double bass

Anne Gillot: bass clarinet

Kaylie Melville: percussion

Arturo Corrales: live electronics

Recorded live at BIFEM, 05/09/2014, Bendigo, Australia.

5) ***Egyptian Love Poem in Nihilist Cipher*** (2014) by James Rushford [audio]

Mauricio Carrasco: guitar/voice

Recorded live at the Ensemble Vortex Concert Season, 04/06/2015, Fonderie Kugler, Geneva, Switzerland.

6) ***Intraluxpixel*** (2015) by Erick Bongcam [video]

Ensemble Vortex

Laurent Bruttin: clarinet

Mauricio Carrasco: e-guitar

Fabio Bergamaschi and Mariano Capona: dancers

Daniel Zea: live electronics

Recorded live at the Ensemble Vortex Concert Season, 05/02/2016, Théâtre Cité Bleue, Geneva, Switzerland.

7) ***The Experiment*** (2015) by David Chisholm [video]

Mauricio Carrasco: performer

Recorded live at the Space Theatre, 13/03/2015, Adelaide Festival Centre, Australia.

8.1) ***Kinecticut*** (2012) by Daniel Zea [video fragments]

Ensemble Vortex

Performers:

Rada Hadjikota-Schleuter, Laurent Bruttin, Daniel Zea, Mauricio Carrasco.

Recorded live at the Ensemble Vortex Concert Season, 31/10/2012, Fonderie Kugler, Geneva, Switzerland.

8.2) ***Kinecticut*** (2012) by Daniel Zea [complete audio]

Ensemble Vortex

Performers:

Rada Hadjikota-Schleuter, Laurent Bruttin, Daniel Zea, Mauricio Carrasco.

Recorded live at the Hall des Chars, Strasbourg, France, 19/10/2012

**B. Exegetic Dissertation relating to the Folio of Performances
(constituting 25% of overall PhD thesis)**

**Monodrama and Music Theatre as Transformative Artistic Experiences.
From a Performative to an Embodied Acting Musician/Guitarist.**

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INTRODUCTION

My PhD folio constitutes close to four hours of audio and video recordings, which trace my artistic trajectory over the past five years and reflect key aspects of my practice as a musician. I have been the instigator of many projects premiered within the timeframe of my PhD, and these form the main case studies of this thesis. All but two of the eight music theatre works or monodramas that make up this folio are newly composed.

While I received a traditional education as a musician at universities and conservatories in Chile and Switzerland, my practice has gradually evolved. I have gone from being a purely instrumental performer towards working as a multidisciplinary artist in theatrical contexts. This evolution was sustained by more than a decade of premiering new works in close collaboration with emerging composers, who often use extended instrumental techniques and new technologies such as live electronics in their compositions. As Robert Adlington points out, through extended techniques “the theatrical element of all music performance [was] enhanced as a performer set about his or her instrument in ways that intruded upon and transgressed the ‘neutral’ codes of the concert ritual.”¹

There has been a degree of generational solidarity, as my collaborations with composers born in the decade of the 1970s have been the most prolific. I identify with their aesthetic directions and I share their search for new expressivity in a musical discourse that often seems to have exhausted its capacity for newness. Common aspects in the music of composers such as Mauricio Pauly, Fernando Garneró and Santiago Díez-Fischer include a deliberate intention of pitch avoidance, privileging noises and scratches produced by the instruments, often via the use of objects. This gives a newer dimension of theatricality to the sound: a certain choreographic quality of the gesture impregnates the music and expands the expressive possibilities of the performer. An acknowledged antecedent for these composers is the celebrated composer Helmut Lachenmann, a pioneer of *musique concrète instrumentale*. Within Lachenmann’s

¹ Adlington, Robert, ‘Music theatre since the 1960s’, in *The Cambridge Companion to Twentieth-Century Opera* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005), pp. 225-226.

oeuvre lies the heavily influential 1977 composition *Salut für Caudwell* for two guitarists. Lachenmann's radical reinvention of the guitar's language and the inclusion in the score of a heavily politicised text by Christopher Caudwell has been the object of study for all these composers and a vocational turning point in my career. Since my first reading of *Salut* I knew that this was the kind of music I wanted to play, and it also marked the beginning of my desire to be a musician/collaborator. No longer satisfied to simply play someone else's music, the personal importance of sharing lives and ideas with living composers became paramount, as if somehow unconsciously following Caudwell's principles from *Illusion and Reality*, the source text of Lachenmann's composition: "We place a simple requirement on you to reconcile life with art and art with life so that your art can come to life."²

² "Wir stellen die einfache Forderung an Euch, das Leben mit der Kunst und die Kunst mit dem Leben in Einklang zu bringen, damit eure Kunst lebendig wird". Translation mine. Christopher Caudwell *Illusion and Reality's* free adaptation by Helmut Lachenmann, *Salut für Caudwell, for two guitarists* (Wiesbaden: Breitkopf & Härtel, 1985), pp. 7-8.

The case studies of this thesis will explore the results of collaborations between artists from diverse disciplines. The following diagram indicates these relationships from the perspective of the performer. Nevertheless, it is important to consider that cross relations exist between the different artists involved in each of the projects:

Georges Aperghis – *Fidélité pour harpe* (1997)/*In-Fidelity for guitar* —

Erick Bongcam – *Intraluxpixel* (2013-2015) —

Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco – *Platero y yo*, op. 190 (1960) —

Arturo Corrales – *BUG* (2006-2008) —

David Chisholm – *The Experiment* (2015) —

James Rushford – *Egyptian Love Poem in Nihilist Cipher* (2014) —

Alexander Schubert – *Sensate Focus* (2014) —

Daniel Zea – *Kinecticut* (2013) —

Salut für Caudwell and its message both stimulated and guided my exploration into Monodrama, as it was the first important work I performed that used extended techniques and spoken text, and also because of a personal political identification with Lachenmann's interpretation of Marxist poet Christopher Caudwell:

There is no neutral artistic universe.

You must choose between an Art unconscious of itself, neither free nor true,
and an Art that knows and expresses its conditions.

We will not stop criticising the bourgeois content of your Art.³

Having this in mind, I have tried to surround my artistic self with composers and artists from theatre and the visual arts, so as to give shape to an exploratory body of work. I have been the instigator of projects that have often been difficult to realise. Normally a timeframe of a couple of years has elapsed between the first conversations and the final creation of the work. I have been actively involved in the process of developing the works, and have participated in creative residencies. I have also exercised a curatorial role, not only in the choice of composers and artists I wanted to develop a work with, but also in proposing collaborations between the different artists involved.

Through the inclusion of text, six of the eight works in my folio present a clear theatricality and can be grouped under the denomination of Monodrama/Melodrama. Throughout this thesis I will "explore the borderline where sound as the bearer of linguistic sense dissolves into sound as the bearer of musical meaning."⁴ This statement by David Osmond-Smith, regarding the music of Luciano Berio, has allowed me to explore the inter-relations between linguistics and music present in the works, and has been complemented by writings by Jean-Jacques Rousseau and Jacques Derrida on the subject. In the

³ *"Es gibt keine neutrale Kunstwelt.*

Ihr müßt wählen zwischen Kunst, die sich ihrer nicht bewußt und unfrei und unwahr ist, und Kunst, die ihre Bedingungen kennt und ausdrückt.

Wir werden nicht aufhören, den bürgerlichen Inhalt eurer Kunst zu kritisieren." Translation mine. Lachenmann, *Salut für Caudwell*, p. 6-7.

⁴ David Osmond-Smith, *Berio* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1991), p. 62.

remaining two works words are absent. However, their theatrical attributes are undeniable. Alexander Schubert's *Sensate Focus* has a choreographic score and a complex system of lights that hides or accentuates the gestures of the musicians; Erick Bongcam's *Intraluxpixel* is a silent melodrama, a *dolente litania a due*, in which the two musicians/patients are confronted by the sadism of the two dancers/nurses: a *duodrama* in which despair and suffering form part of the human condition and where words become redundant.

Reading signs that belong to different art forms raises questions of significance and identity: How does a performer build a new *sonic self*, given that the sound of the instrument, that essential aspect that takes us a lifetime to develop and grow confident with, can be suddenly transformed by the "intrusion" of external elements? These can include spoken or sung text, electronic sounds and the presence of video and other visual manifestations that can disturb our perceptions. Therefore, the semiotic connotations of a performer's work in a broader cross-arts environment will also be explored. As Naomi Cumming has pointed out, "when a new work deliberately extends the possibilities of a tradition [...] a further source for uncertainty is introduced in knowing the degree to which an inherited term is apposite."⁵

⁵ Naomi Cumming, *The Sonic Self: Musical Subjectivity and Signification* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2000), p. 70.

**Melodramatic/Monodramatic voices,
*the alternation or simultaneity between spoken word and music.***

Even if both Melodrama and Monodrama have commonly been used in an interchangeable manner: the authoritative *Die Musik in Geschichte und Gegenwart* (MGG) has opted for an entry covering both categories, entitled: “Monodram → Melodram”. However, for the purpose of this research, some differentiations between the terms need to be established.

While at times historically and conceptually opaque, Melodrama usually employs spoken word in combination with instrumental music as its principal technique. As with many musical forms that emerged during the Classical period (the first official melodrama being Rousseau’s *Pygmalion* in 1762), the genre crystallised during the nineteenth century.

For the purpose of this thesis I have commenced my study with the first of four books of Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco’s *Platero y yo*, op. 190 for narrator and guitar, which is referred to in Jacqueline Waeber’s list of melodramas as the only example of the genre that features the guitar as a soloist-accompanying instrument.⁶ I have drawn together a performance edition of the work, based on comparisons between the composer’s manuscript, the Bèrben Edition, and Andrés Segovia’s manuscripts, discussion of which is provided in Appendix I. In the dissertation I examine how *Platero y yo* aligns with Ben Singer’s five constituent elements or tropes of melodrama: strong pathos, moral polarity, exaggerated emotions, narrative devices that are implausible, convoluted or outrageous, and the inclusion of forces of nature.⁷

Originally used to designate forms of melodrama for one character, Monodrama has acquired psychological connotations related to trauma and hysteria by

⁶ ‘Le Mélodrame de Rousseau à aujourd’hui, list of melodramas’, in Jacqueline Waeber, *En Musique dans le Texte. Le Mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg* (Paris: Van Dieren, 2006), pp. 457-470.

⁷ Ben Singer, *Melodrama and Modernity: Early Sensational Cinema and Its Contexts* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2001), pp. 44-48.

focussing on the interior life of the solo figure. That makes it more suitable for the rest of my case studies. Monodrama has been defined as “an experiential mode that seeks to provide the audience with the opportunity to have a ‘co-experience’ with the protagonist”, and one that “attempts to transplant the audience into the protagonist’s psyche” by “exposing the state of mind of a traumatised individual to listeners.”⁸ That aspect of Monodrama coalesced at the start of the twentieth century, with figures such as Arnold Schoenberg strongly influenced by psychoanalysis and the German cabaret. This style of Monodrama continues to inform subsequent manifestations of the genre, as will be discussed in relation to the works explored in this dissertation.

In Georges Aperghis’ *Fidélité* the text and music are united in the same persona. Differing from the works of Mauricio Kagel, who sought humour through the absurd by instructing musicians to undertake unexpected theatrical actions, Aperghis continues the tradition of monodrama as a psychological journey. Due to the absence of repertoire for guitar by this important and transformative composer, I have transcribed his work for harp *Fidélité*. Through the performance of the work I will seek to translate the female hysterical harpist into a male hysterical guitarist. Throughout my discussion of the works in the folio, I examine traces of hysteria, alienation and trauma. After having presented my *Fidélité* transcription, theatre director Jude Anderson proposed that we collaborate on an English version of the work, to be directed by her in a fetishist milieu and with actress Sapidah Kian as my Master, and I will discuss this process of reinterpretation of a classic work of music theatre.

In Part II of the exegesis I focus on the newly composed music theatre works that make up the folio. Mirroring Aperghis in elements such as the complexity of the writing and in the twitchy and dismembered treatment of the text, James Rushford’s *Egyptian Love Poem in Nihilist Cipher* presents an engagement with Monodrama by a new generation of composers. The commission was made possible thanks to Arts Victoria funding, and allowed for a close collaboration

⁸ Jessica Payette, *Seismographic Screams: “Ertwartung”’s reverberations through twentieth-century culture* (Ann Arbor: UMI Dissertations Publishing, 2008), pp. 138-139.

process through to the première in June 2015 in Geneva, which will be explored below.

Two of the case studies correspond to more ambitious projects. Along with the composer-performer collaborations, these works include the participation of artists from other disciplines, including dramatists, theatre directors, dramaturges, visual and media artists. The realisation of these projects has taken several years, and I will examine the varied processes of collaboration and development.

The first of these larger projects, *BUG trilogy*, was composed by Arturo Corrales in three different stages, as a concerto where each one of its movements was composed at a different time. This strategy allowed for the building of a larger form with limited funding. I have been able to premiere each one of the movements separately, from the first for guitar and electronics to the third for quintet. The overall work spans an arc over which the electronics slowly fade away while the threatening presence of new instruments accentuates the isolation and desolation of the guitarist character, the main character. Once the work was written, we decided to invite theatre director Christophe Bergon to work on a *mise en scène* to build a coherent show out of this trilogy.

The second, David Chisholm's *The Experiment*, is the most onerous and ambitious project in which I have been involved. In this case the performer, the guitarist/reciter, is part of a larger group of collaborators. These include a playwright, composer, visual artist, media artist and dramaturge as the main collaborators, while sound artists and instrument builders have contributed to different stages of this production. I will reflect on how the collaborative process between artists from different fields converges in the creation of a finished work of art.

The final section of the exegesis explores new forms of monodrama/music theatre through my continuous collaboration with composer Daniel Zea. His work *Kinecticut*, sound choreography for four performers and four computers with their respective Kinects could be construed as a Monodrama. Even though the work is for a quartet, the important aspect on *Kinecticut* is the interior life of the solo figure, one of the main characteristics of Monodrama.

VORTEX

Four of the works of this folio have been prepared as part of my work with the Ensemble Vortex. Reaching the end of our studies at Geneva Conservatory, a group of composers and performers wanted to continue our collaboration and formed the Ensemble. Vortex has focused on the commission and creation of new works written by emerging composers with an accent on the use of extended instrumental techniques and interactivity with live electronics. Gradually our interest as performers and composers started to tend towards the exploration of new possibilities in music theatre. This is the context in which *BUG Trilogy*, *Intraluxpixel*, *Kinecticut* and *Sensate Focus* were programmed as part of the ensemble's concert seasons during the past five years.

Part One – Music Theatre and Monodrama/Melodrama.

From the Melodramatic tradition to the Appearance of the Acting Musician.

Preface

The first part of this thesis is divided into three sections, each of which explores a different Music Theatre work.

-1.1. *Platero y yo op. 190* (1960), first quire, by Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco, lyrics by Juan Ramón Jiménez. Melodrama for narrator and guitar.

-1.2. *Sensate Focus* (2014), for e-guitar, bass clarinet, percussion, violin, live electronics and animated lights by Alexander Schubert.

-1.3. *Fidélité pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme* (1982) by Georges Aperghis. This work has been adapted as part of this thesis as *Fidélité pour guitariste seul regardé par une femme ou un homme*.

1.1. MUSICAL MELODRAMA FOR NARRATOR AND GUITAR

Platero y yo, an Andalusian Elegy

“The giant murmuring upon which language opens and thus becomes image, becomes imaginary, becomes a speaking depth, an indistinct plenitude which is empty.”

Maurice Blanchot, from *The Space of Literature*.

“Platero, if some day I throw myself into the well, it will not be for death’s sake, believe me, but only the more quickly to attain the stars.”

Juan Ramón Jiménez, from *Platero y yo*.

Platero y yo is arguably the most important work of Juan Ramón Jiménez, who obtained the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1956. He revisited the work throughout his life, and it remains to this day a well-known text for children and adults in the Spanish-speaking world. Platero “is a small donkey, a soft, hairy donkey”⁹. The poet narrates episodes of his adventures with Platero in a landscape framed by nature: flowers and animals have a stronger presence than humans who appear as a constant threat, with children being the only exception (as they are saved by their innocence). *Platero y yo* also exists as a Melodrama, one of the only melodramas for guitar and narrator of the repertoire. Composer Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco chose twenty-eight of the 138 prose-written poems that constitute the complete text to create a melodrama that extends to nearly two hours. I have chosen the first volume of *Platero y yo*, that consists of seven poems, for the purpose of this research.

Castelnuovo-Tedesco lived for years in exile in the USA after leaving Italy because of persecution due to being Jewish. His statement: “Exile is the general

⁹ “Platero es pequeño, peludo, suave”. Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Juan Ramón Jiménez, *Platero y yo (Platero and I)*, I. Platero, English translation by Eloise Roach (Ancona: Edizioni Bèrben, 1972), p. 5.

rehearsal of death”¹⁰ resonates deeply in all of us who have been or are still expatriates. Jiménez would also suffer exile later in his life. But an inner exile was already present before that, the exile from the adults’ world. He builds a “pantheistic mysticism”¹¹ constituted by animals and nature as a shelter from the outside cruel world in war and crisis. Children are viewed as the only worthwhile part of humanity, mostly because they are not yet corrupted. They give the poet the strength to face the inexorable reality of death in a bucolic refuge of butterflies, birds, happy children and a sweet donkey in his celebrated work *Platero y yo*.

These elements of Jiménez’ universe appear in the seven poems selected by Castelnuovo-Tedesco for the first quire of his op. 190. A pantheistic mysticism as well as a “seasonal cycle of birth, death and regeneration”¹² are omnipresent in *Platero*, and the first seven poems are no exception. They include the following elements:

- A suggestion of reincarnation through the figure of a butterfly flying near Platero’s grave: “a white butterfly, soft and smooth as waxen petals, fluttered gently, like a soul, from lily to lily.”¹³
- A fusion between the poet and Platero: “And suddenly I remembered Platero, whom, though on him, I had forgotten, as if he were part of my body.”¹⁴

¹⁰ Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco, *Una vita di musica*, typescript, Vol. I, cited in *Music and the Holocaust: Jews and Music in Fascist Italy*, accessed October 15, 2015, <http://holocaustmusic.ort.org/politics-and-propaganda/jews-and-music-in-fascist-italy/>

¹¹ Pierre Ullmann, *A contrapuntal Method for Analyzing Spanish Literature* (Potomac: Scripta Humanistica, 1988), p. 234.

¹² Michael Predmore cited in ‘Divining the Distant: The Poetics of Platero y Yo’ by Raymond Skyrme, *Romance Quarterly*, Vol. 47 no. 4 (Fall 2000), p. 195.

¹³ “una leve mariposa blanca, que antes no había visto, revolaba insistentemente, igual que un alma, de lirio en lirio”. Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez, *Platero y yo*, VII. Melancolía – Melancholy, p. 38.

¹⁴ “Y pensé, de pronto, en Platero, que aunque iba debajo de mí, se me había, como si fuera mi cuerpo, olvidado”. Ibid, III. Retorno – Return, p. 18.

- A fusion between the poet and nature: “see how my forehead, my shoulders, my hands, are covered with roses.”¹⁵
- An association between religiosity and nature: “It might be thought that roses are being thrown down from the seven heavens of paradise.”¹⁶
- A pantheistic reference: “I go down to the garden and sing thanks to the God of the blue day”¹⁷ He refers to the gentle God, not to the “God of the dark night”, the one that takes the lives of his loved ones.
- The superiority of animals to human adults in a pantheistic context: “Well content, with no fatal obligations, with no Olympus to enrapture nor Avernus to terrify them, with no morality but their own nor any God but the blue, they are my brothers, my sweet brothers.”¹⁸

All these elements make us wonder if Pierre Ullmann in his “A Contrapuntal Method for Analyzing Spanish Literature” is correct when stating:

When we realise that *Platero y yo* is autobiographical and that the author is the protagonist, we cannot help wondering whether Juan Ramón’s *symboliste* concretisation of the Christ metaphor in his own person is not due to some narcissistic derangement. Only if we recognise the author’s pantheistic mysticism can we cast off such a suspicion.¹⁹

While I agree with Ullmann in terms of Jiménez’ pantheistic mysticism, I do not think *Platero* is autobiographical, even if it is inspired by his hometown in the Andalusian countryside. His constant disinterest in humans (except children)

¹⁵ The translation doesn’t give the exact idea of the original: “Mira cómo se me llenan de rosas la frente, los hombros, las manos”. The poet uses a reflexive form *se me llenan* that indicates a symbiosis between his body and nature, in this case the roses. A more appropriate translation would be “see how my forehead, my shoulders, my hands get filled with roses”. Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez, *Platero y yo*, II. Angelus, p.10.

¹⁶ “De las siete galerías del Paraíso se creyera que tiran rosas a la tierra”. Ibid, II. Angelus, p. 12.

¹⁷ “Salgo al huerto y canto gracias al Dios del día azul”. Ibid, IV. Primavera – Spring, p. 20.

¹⁸ Again the translation fails to give the exact idea of the poet: his appeal to humans is much more clear than the translation *nor Avernus to terrify them* “ni esos avernos que extasían o que amedrantan a los pobres hombres esclavos”. A better translation would be: “nor Avernus to captivate or frighten those poor slave humans”). Ibid, VI. Gorriones – Sparrows, p. 31.

¹⁹ Ullmann, *A Contrapuntal Method for Analyzing Spanish Literature*, p. 234.

separates him from the figure of Jesus, and sharing the love for children, animals and nature is not enough to insinuate that the poet is trying to establish a metaphor with Christ. When Ullmann attempts to psychoanalyse the poet by saying that he suffered from a narcissistic derangement, it makes one wonder if that state is not underscore the qualities of poetry itself: in order to dive into one's unconscious dark areas to *write from the soul*, doesn't every poet need to be at least a little *narcissisticly* deranged?

Even if the poet only mentions the donkey Platero's death explicitly in the last of the seven episodes, *Melancolía*, the general tone of the prose-written poems is indeed melancholic. Jiménez tries to cope with the grief and mourning produced by his father's death that led him into severe depression, his salvation being the bucolic idealisation of rural landscapes, animals and children. *Platero* narrates the relation between the poet and the donkey over the course of a year, from Spring to Spring. This season's choice can be explained by the blossoming of nature as an alternative to a definitive death: things reborn, the spirit of the donkey once gone appears in a butterfly, while the poet asks Mother Earth: "have you forgotten me, perhaps? Tell me Platero, do you still remember me?"²⁰ Michael Predmore's statement that, "*Platero y yo* displays a structural unity shaped by the seasonal cycle of birth, death and regeneration" is pertinent in that it helps to explain how Jiménez gave coherence to the 138 short prose written poems that would otherwise have looked like separate vignettes.

Jiménez' poetry can have the appearance of fairy-tale escapism. Written in 1914, while Spain was experiencing a huge economic crisis, the poet finds his shelter in animals, children and nature and deliberately avoids the grown up world:

And when people – poor wretched people - go to church on Sundays, locking their doors behind them, they [the sparrows], in a glad example of riteless love, suddenly come, with their fresh and jovial shrilling, to the gardens of the closed

²⁰ "¿me habrás, quizá, olvidado? Platero, dime: ¿te acuerdas aún de mí?" Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez, *Platero y yo*, VII. Melancolía – Melancholy, p. 36-37.

houses in which some poet, whom they know well, and a tender small donkey
[...] watch them with fraternal love.²¹

The poet is mourning his father's death and he is living through convoluted times, he is suffering from what Freud describes in *Mourning and Melancholia* as the "loss of some abstraction which has taken place of one, such as one's country, liberty, an ideal and so on"²². This state of mourning puts the narrator into a melancholic frame of mind, where the outside world loses its interest, and instead an idyllic world is recreated. His recovery from depression in his hometown of Moguer was his source of inspiration. The later writing of *Platero* crystallises the experience, with Blanchot commenting that:

Memories are necessary, but only that they may be forgotten: in order that in this forgetfulness – in the silence of a profound metamorphosis – there might at least be born a word, the first word of a poem.²³

The difference between *Platero* and the rest of the Monodramas presented in this thesis is the absence of trauma and hysteria, present in the works by Aperghis, Bongcam, Corrales, Chisholm and Zea. Instead, trauma is supplanted by mourning, and hysteria by melancholia, in both text and music. The tonalities and modalities used by Castelnuovo-Tedesco for the music of *Platero* reinforce the nostalgic and rural view of Spain in the text as well as the cultural image of guitar as a folkloric period instrument.

In *Platero* the spoken word is delivered by the narrator and the instrumental music by the guitarist, but apart from this basic melodramatic principle, is *Platero* a real melodrama and if so, what does it have in common with other

²¹ "Y cuando las gentes, ¡las pobres gentes!, se van a misa los domingos, cerrando las puertas, ellos, en un alegre ejemplo de amor sin rito, se viene de pronto, con su algarabía fresca y jovial, al jardín de las casas cerradas, en las que algún poeta, que ya conocen bien, y algún burrillo tierno [...] los contemplan fraternales". Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez, *Platero y yo*, VI. Gorriones – Sparrows, pp. 33-34.

²² Sigmund Freud, 'Mourning and Melancholia', *The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud*, Vol. XIV (1914-1916), translated by James Strachey (London: The Hogarth Press, 1957), p. 243.

²³ Maurice Blanchot, *The Space of Literature* (Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1982), translated by Ann Smock, p. 86.

melodramas from different genres such as cinema or theatre? As Ben Singer observes: “melodrama’s nature as a cluster concept means that the genre’s key constitutive factors can appear in any number of different configurations. One might have two completely distinct combinations – sharing none of the same elements – yet both warranting the label melodrama.”²⁴ To specify the common aspects between melodramas, Singer proposes five essential elements that may or may not necessarily be shared by different manifestations of the genre:

- 1) **strong pathos.** Probably the aspect melodramas share the most, the emotions are *à fleur de peau*, ready to explode, to blossom and flourish, being part of common expressions such as “don’t be melodramatic” to determine an excess of emotions. However, emotions can be of different kinds depending on the melodrama: in *Platero*, text and music create a nostalgic, sweet atmosphere, with rare emotive explosions.
- 2) **moral polarity.** In this aspect *Platero* is very clear: adult humans are corrupt, while children and animals are innocent and worth approaching, and this is framed in a landscape of bucolic nature.
- 3) **exaggerated emotions.** *Platero* certainly presents a strong pathos, the relation between the poet and the tender donkey *Platero* is a source of emotions, though not necessarily exaggerated.
- 4) **narrative devices that are implausible, convoluted and outrageous.** The pantheistic mysticism of *Platero* gives qualities to animals and nature out of the daily sphere: a donkey is not only useful for its work on a farm but becomes the loving poet’s best friend and confidant, while butterflies have a mission of showing the spiritual presence of the lost ones. People are redundant and less significant, except for children who can touch the enchanted world because they are still innocent creatures.
- 5) **the inclusion of forces of nature.** In *Platero*, nature has a preponderant role. “Everywhere the countryside bursts open to a bubbling of new and wholesome life”²⁵. Seasons change the landscape and the mood of the

²⁴ Singer, *Melodrama and Modernity: Early Sensational Cinema and Its Contexts*, p. 54.

²⁵ “Por doquiera, el campo se abre en estallidos, en crujidos, en hervidero de vida sana y nueva” Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez, *Platero y yo*, IV. La Primavera – Spring, p. 23.

poet, nature provides all the elements for Jiménez poetry: the birds, the butterflies, the animals. These constitute the uncontaminated heaven far from men that inspires Jiménez and where he finds shelter.

The psychological working of colour

The above subtitle is taken from Vassily Kandinsky's book *The Art of Spiritual Harmony*, which includes the following text: "the superficial impression of varied colour may be the starting point of a whole chain of related sensations."²⁶ I find in this quotation parallels with Castelnuovo-Tedesco's more impressionistic conception of colour, that is less in accord with the period in which he composed *Platero y yo* (1960). The score constantly accompanies the narrator's and even the donkey's mood (the work opens with the rather equine indication *trotting*). Dramatic changes in tonality occur in perfect synchrony with the poetry - dissonance and serialism are substituted here by consonance and harmony. This apparent distance from the more fashionable compositional styles of the mid twentieth century perfectly parallels the aesthetic of Jiménez' poetry. In this it mirrors the work of another artist of the time, who was also interested in melodrama, the cinema director Nicholas Ray: "Ray's work is romantic: he aspires to another world, to a kind of absolute, but knowing that this world doesn't exist, not anymore. Or said otherwise: that the earth that I would like to live in only exists in my certainty and it can't be found anywhere."²⁷ This chimeric notion of *Paradise Lost*, shared by Castelnuovo-Tedesco, Jiménez and Ray can be partially explained by the writer and composer's exile. In the case of Ray "exile is the modality of life itself. Focusing on a desire that renders

²⁶ Wassily Kandinsky, *The Art of Spiritual Harmony* (London: Constable and Company Limited, 1914), p. 47.

²⁷ "L'oeuvre de Ray est romantique: on y aspire à un autre monde, une sorte d'absolu. Mais en sachant toutefois que ce monde n'est pas, n'est plus. Ou plutôt: la terre que j'aimerais habiter n'existe que dans ma certitude qu'elle ne peut être trouvée nulle part." Own translation. Jean-Christophe Ferrari, 'Tendresse pour les violents: Sur quelques personnages de Nicholas Ray pour lesquels il n'est pas de retour possible', *Positif* 662, April 2016, p. 100.

obsessive and unassimilable, colour shows the impossibility of all possession and the impossibility of renouncing.”²⁸

This uprooting from childhood in the case of the poet and from an ideal musical universe where melody and harmony rule over chaos and experimentation in the case of the composer, successfully conjoin in the many movements of this musical monodrama. For instance, the inevitable mourning that emanates from the composer’s statement that “exile is the general rehearsal of death” perfectly underscores Jiménez’ poetry in the last movement of this first quire, *Melancholy*: the moment in which the poet goes with a group of children to visit Platero’s grave.

To classify Castelnuovo-Tedesco and Jiménez’ *Platero y yo* as a Melodrama is therefore justified, not only because of the nature of the text but essentially because of the genre that mixes spoken word and music. However, relatively few people think of *Platero y yo* as a melodrama, since it is better known as an episodic prose-written poem than as a music-accompanied form, even if the poetry itself contains melodramatic aspects as described above.

As part of my research I have included in Appendix One notes on the revisions to the edition of the musical score that I have undertaken. These were necessary to perform the score of *Platero y yo* with the same dexterity and expression with which actress Sapidah Kian approached the text. Our interpretative intention did not consist of merely making the music accompany the poetry, as that would have diminished Castelnuovo-Tedesco’s compositional intentions and would have gone against the best melodramatic tradition. Instead, it was necessary to aim for a symbiosis between instrumentalist and narrator that could result in a shared expression where text and music could become one.

²⁸ “L’exil [est la] modalité même de la vie. En chiffrant ainsi un désir qu’elle rend obsédant et inassimilable, la couleur montre, ensemble, l’impossibilité de toute possession et l’impossibilité d’y renoncer.” Own translation. Frank Kausch, ‘Vanité de la Clairvoyance: à partir de la couleur chez Nicholas Ray’, *Positif* 662, p. 102.

1.2. THE PERFORMATIVE ACTING MUSICIAN

Alexander Schubert's renewed vision of German Instrumental Theatre.

“Music theatre is theatre that is music driven.”

Eric Salzman and Thomas Desi, from *The New Music Theater: Seeing the Voice, Hearing the Body*.

Mauricio Kagel's development of Instrumental Theatre through his early works such as *Sonant* (1960) and *Match* (1966) explored “physicality and kinesis of playing”, “central to the production of music”²⁹. *Match* gives athletic qualities to performers as the two cellists are confronted in a match with the percussionist in the middle as a referee. In this context, the musicians can be identified as *Performative Acting Musicians*, a term that suggests the “musician does not need to become an actor; he is one already, although most musicians who have gone through the traditional western musical education would not emphasise this.”³⁰ Performing music theatre works with conservatory-trained musicians requires a conscious effort to revert the prejudices learnt during those years of training. The classical/romantic aspiration of rendering the performer “invisible” in order to serve the music as a vessel through whom the audience will get intact the composer's original message does not serve the theatricality needed to perform such music theatre works. This search for invisibility that intends to “tame” young and grown up musicians, by making them play behind a curtain on orchestral auditions, making them play exactly the same repertoire over and over again in competitions and examinations, and even by making them wear a dress code that aims to meld the musician's body with the stage by wearing dark colours. This can create a great deal of stress and frustration in students and professional musicians whose artistic aspirations are different, and in the past,

²⁹ Haakon Thelin, *A new world of sounds – recent advancements in contemporary double bass techniques*, accessed May 3, 2016, <https://haakonthelein.com>

³⁰ Christa Brüstle, ‘Composing with Raw Materials: Daniel Ott's Music-theatre Portraits and Landscapes’, in *Composed Theatre: Aesthetics, Practices, Processes*, Matthias Rebstock, David Roesner (eds.), (Bristol: Intellect, 2012), p. 261.

“the performer who sought to assert his or her individuality over and above this ritual risked accusations of charlatanism.”³¹

If Kagel’s Instrumental Theatre was in part a response to the perfect pure sound of concert electronic music, a way of accentuating the human touch of imperfection and differentiation between performances, in emerging composers interested in music theatre the use of electronics constitutes an ally and not an enemy. Composers such as Jennifer Walshe, Patricia Alessandrini and Alexander Schubert use the infinite possibilities of interaction between acoustics and electronics that software such as Max/MSP and Ableton Live can offer. These programs are used by Alexander Schubert in his 2014 work *Sensate Focus* for electric guitar, bass clarinet, percussion, violin, live electronics and animated light. The musicians follow a click track that guides them through a score of notes and gestures, and the theatricality of the work is given by the score itself through specific indications of improvisation and movements strictly limited in time by the click track. The effectiveness of the work depends on that interaction, for instance in this section the interactive lights are programmed to be on only during the “frozen” 4/4 bars, the musicians therefore improvise in total darkness:

Fig. 1. Alexander Schubert, *Sensate Focus* (2014), self-published score, bars 507-515.

³¹ Adlington, ‘Music theatre since the 1960s’, p. 225.

The use of humour and irony is reminiscent of Kagel's Instrumental Theatre. For instance, Schubert references video games such as *Guitar Hero* (where the player simulates playing an instrument), by asking the musicians to play in the air imitating the electronics. In a similar vein, Kagel made Caucasian classically-trained musicians use tribal painting on their faces in his work *Exotica*.

Fig. 2. Alexander Schubert, *Sensate Focus* (2014), self-published score, bars 183-184.

Fig. 3. Mauricio Kagel, *Exotica* (CD Cover), Deutsche Grammophon, 1994.

Likewise Schubert's instructions to his musicians to "consider yourself a robot, a puppet or similar"³² follow a certain absurd tendency present in Kagel's work, in particular the composition of *Staatstheater*, a ballet for non-dancers.

Both Kagel and Schubert work with the human material at hand: Western classically-trained musicians. By making them execute unusual actions they accentuate the absurd, specially when their works are programmed among other academic contemporary works that don't explore theatrical aspects. These works are performed by the same capable musicians who are trained to play complex and intricate scores, although they usually look more comfortable playing hyper complex repertoire than these works by Kagel or Schubert. This underscores the composers' intentions: they are not searching for actors but they want to explore theatrical aspects with their musicians so they can look slightly out of place. This is the starting point for this folio of work: the *acting*

³² Alexander Schubert, *Sensate Focus*, self-published score, 2014, p. 3.

musician that starts training in music theatre by being a *performative acting musician* – following and executing the composer’s musical and theatrical instructions – will evolve into the *embodied acting musician* who will need to incorporate acting skills in performance. These acting tools will allow him/her to understand and build a character’s psyche and physique, aspects that are vital to the successful performance of the rest of the works in the folio by Aperghis, Corrales, Chisholm, Bongcam and Zea.

1.3. TOWARDS THE EMBODIED ACTING MUSICIAN

Integration of Music and Text in the same Persona in Georges Aperghis' *Fidélité*.

"Music appears when language reaches its own limits"

Georges Aperghis, from *Interview with Georges Aperghis*.

"There is not music before language. Music is born of voice and not of sound. No pre linguistic sonority can, according to Rousseau, open the time of music. In the beginning is the song"

Jacques Derrida, from *Of Grammatology*.

The mix of declamation and music makes of Monodrama a genre that has something of the ancestral. Even if the first "official" Monodrama/Melodrama was Jean Jacques Rousseau's *Pygmalion* (1762), it is possible to trace and link Monodrama to a tradition that goes back to the Greek tragedy. However, in Jacqueline Waeber's opinion that association can be risky: "We strive to find predecessors to *Pygmalion*. That exercise is however quite dangerous, because of trying too hard to go back in time we can arrive at medieval miracle plays, or even ancient Greek drama: *Pygmalion* was considered by many of Rousseau's contemporaries as an imitation of that model."³³

When Derrida says that "there is not music before language"³⁴ he is referring to primitive man and how both music and language originated. There is a certain resemblance between Derrida speculating on the origins of language and music

³³ "On s'évertue encore à trouver des prédécesseurs à ce mélodrame. L'exercice est toutefois assez dangereux, car à trop vouloir remonter les pistes on finit par arriver aux miracles médiévaux, pour ne rien dire du drame grec antique: le *Pygmalion* fut d'ailleurs considéré par nombre de ses contemporains comme une imitation de ce modèle." Translation mine, Waeber, *En musique dans le texte. Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 17.

³⁴ Jacques Derrida, *Of Grammatology*, translated by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak (Baltimore: The John Hopkins University Press, corrected edition, 1997), p. 195.

and Aperghis referring to his own work in terms of music appearing “when language reaches its own limits.”³⁵

This parallel is intensified when Derrida claims that “If music awakens in song, if it is initially uttered, *vociferated*, it is because, like all speech, it is born in passion. That is to say in the transgression of need by desire and the awakening of pity by imagination. Everything proceeds from this inaugural distinction”³⁶. In his 1982 work for harp *Fidélité*, Aperghis creates a text that goes from spoken to sung text, passing through the liminal area of *Sprechstimme*, which is neither sung nor spoken, but spoken with a certain pitch. The text is declaimed calmly at the beginning, and it gets more and more agitated through a prodigious sense of theatricality towards an “uttered, vociferated” text. This requires passion to be transmitted by the performer, who needs to forget the conventions of traditional concert music in order to enter into a state of controlled hysteria, controlled because she/he needs to continue playing hyper complex passages while she/he is projecting a nervous breakdown.

While in traditional Melodrama there is a separation between the reciter/singer and the instrumentalist (as was the case in *Platero y yo* op. 190 by Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco), in *Fidélité* the text and the music are performed by the same persona. And this persona must be a musician, as well as an actor. Far from the aforementioned examples by Mauricio Kagel and Alexander Schubert, the musician is not making actions “as if he/she was acting”, but he/she needs to embody the acting situation. This requires from him/her an investment in the acting part that is equal to or greater than that given to the musical part. This figure of the **Embodied Acting Musician** is applicable to the rest of this folio’s case studies.

Aperghis has spoken of his attitude towards the production of his music theatre works:

I take time to rehearse the works of music theatre. I can get lost and find again myself with the performers. It is a completely different attitude. I take the risks of

³⁵ Georges Aperghis cited by Tarek Kai in *Interview with Georges Aperghis*, accessed January 8, 2016, <http://www.internationales-musikinstitut.de/en/summer-course/archive2014/blog-en/1312-tarek-kai.html>

³⁶ Derrida, *Of Grammatology*, p. 195.

arriving with fragments of text and music, and to finish the work in the theatre. Sewing together the fragments and the lights and the texts and the behaviours of the performers.³⁷

What Aperghis points out is the essentially different rehearsal process between his music theatre works and his purely instrumental works. The collaboration here is real – going well beyond the usual practice of sending a PDF of a finished score to the musicians a couple of weeks before the premiere. Rather, it is a process whereby the music and text are integrated and assimilated, or *embodied*, during the rehearsal period. This manner of producing work is shared by Bongcam, Corrales, Chisholm and Zea works that will be discussed later in this exegesis.

My first presentation of *Fidélité* took place during the Guitar Perspectives series at the University of Melbourne in 2015. When I had previously seen the work performed, the harpist behaved as someone with no goodwill, almost as if she was handicapped, incapable of moving or undertaking any actions until she was finally seated, assisted by the man, who also brought the harp close to her. The instructions in the score suggest that attitude:

An older man enters the room, honourable, well dressed, holding the harpist by her wrist.

Even that gaoler gesture must be elegant.

The harpist is dressed in black, simply but elegantly.

He will release her wrist only once she has been seated – helped by him. He will sit down a bit further away.

He will appear to be listening and he will stay inscrutable during the whole piece.

He will never look at her.³⁸

³⁷ Kai, *Interview with Georges Aperghis*.

³⁸ “Entre un homme agé, digne, bien habillé, tenant par le poignet la harpiste.

Même ce geste de geôlier doit être elegant.

La harpiste est habillé de noir, simplement mais avec elegance.

Il ne lui lâchera le poignet que lorsqu'elle sera installée – aidée par lui - à sa chaise. Lui, ira s'asseoir un peu plus loin.

Il semblera écouter et restera indéchiffrable pendant toute la pièce.

Il ne la regardera jamais.”

Translation mine. Georges Aperghis, *Fidélité, pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme*, 1982 (self-published score), p. 1.

After reading this introduction, it is hard not to think of the misogynistic character of the work, in which the woman is treated as a kind of puppet, and where all her movements are conducted by the “elegant dignified older man”. This patronising patriarchal posture corresponds very well within the heterosexual male-dominated milieu of contemporary concert music. To push the gender inversion of the transcription we chose to intensify the submissive character of the female harpist/male guitarist by the use of a blindfold and a soft bondage on his wrists. That’s how my “master” - the female actor Sapidah Kian - guided me onto the stage. Only after having seated me and put the guitar on my lap does she take off the blindfold so I can start playing.

The Guitar Perspectives concert was attended by theatre director Jude Anderson. She was casting acts for a series of Live Arts Auctions that were programmed on March 2016 during the Festival of Live Arts at Arts House in Melbourne under the name “Complete Smut,” and she selected us. This is the text Anderson wrote to “sell” the work to their potential interested “buyers”:

An inversion of ‘Fidelity’ by renowned Greco/French composer and director Aperghis, ‘In-Fidelity’ inverts Aperghis’s male/female sado-masochistic relationship and transforms it into an encounter with voyeurism and male hysteria climaxing in a petite mort.

If a last utterance is described as an ejaculation, what is the musical equivalent?

Leading international experimental guitarist Mauricio Carrasco gets his instrument off in the presence of celebrated actor Sapidah Kian for this tightly strung musical extasis.³⁹

It is clear then that the adaptation of *Fidélité* into *In-Fidelity* has a sexual connotation, as a form of provocation and of somehow ridiculing the misogynistic aspect of the original work. And director Jude Anderson, with the complicity of the performers and her whole team, pushed the envelope. A sado-masochistic interpretation of the work wasn’t just insinuated but openly explored. Costumes designed by Mila Faranov showed a sexually provocative Master conducting (through a three metre dog leash) her Slave/guitarist, who

³⁹ Jude Anderson, *In-Fidelity*, *COMPLETE SMUT art auction Catalogue / Punctum*, accessed March 20, 2017, <http://www.punctum.com.au/fidelity>

was dressed in black PVC one-piece overalls that resembled latex. The leash was pulled at certain moments where the piece suggests asphyxiation, creating a convincing simulation of asphyxia, not just an insinuated one.

The indication by Aperghis that the man will never look at the harpist wasn't completely respected either. The studied cross of regards throughout the piece was meticulously rehearsed and represented in a continuous emotional feedback between the master and her slave. This sort of silent dialectic tension between master and slave is explored by Lacan on one of his famous *séminaires*:

What remains is indeed, in effect, the essence of the master, namely, that he does not know what he wants. There you have what constitutes the true structure of the discourse of the master. The slave knows lots of things, but what he knows even better still is what the master wants, even if the latter does not know it, which is the usual case, for without that he would not be a master. The slave knows it, and that is what his function as slave is. It is also for this that it works, for, all the same, it has worked for a fair while. The fact that the all-knowledge has moved into the place of the master is something that, far from throwing light on it, obscures a bit more what is in question, namely, truth.⁴⁰

Anderson takes Aperghis' music as an inspiration and starting point. She plays with the ambiguity of who it is that rules in a master/slave relationship. While the slave (guitarist) is much more active during the piece than the master, the master gives in at certain moments to what the slave is asking for: asphyxiation, bondage, or mistreatment. This interpretation is certainly far from Aperghis' original intention, where the harpist is not a real slave but a vulnerable creature that has a fit of hysteria while performing/embodying *Fidélité*.

The way Aperghis treats the text draws directly on the Theatre of the Absurd, especially the work of Samuel Beckett: "Beckett [...] used to work in a very musical manner. There are the same substances that come back like a spiral. There are things that are being added, others that are taken apart."⁴¹ In the spirit of Beckett, Aperghis constructs a text that doesn't make much sense most of the

⁴⁰ Jacques Lacan, *Le séminaire. Livre XVII, L'envers de la psychanalyse: 1969-1970*. English translation by Russell Grigg. (Paris, Ed. Du Seuil, 2007), p. 34.

⁴¹ Kai, *Interview with Georges Aperghis*.

time, creating a real dramatic peak when suddenly one coherent sentence is said. He builds musical motifs that correspond with a certain part of text, and the dramatic tension is present from the first pages, through the use of extreme *accelerandi* or *ritardandi* in the space of just one or a couple of bars.

Example 1. Georges Aperghis, *Fidélité* (1982), self-published score, bar 19.

In-Fidelity was translated into English to make it more accessible to the Melbourne audience, and it is the recording of this version that is included in this folio. For the transcription (see appendix 2), I kept the original French text (which remains my choice at the time of performing the work), with my English translation included below the original text. I have respected Aperghis' original French text, making only slight adjustments between text and music when they didn't align as well as in the original.

Hysteria on show

“A theatre where the animal savagery provokes fear and breaks with one stroke the ceremonious codes of the bourgeois world.”

Ariel Schweitzer, from *Cahiers du Cinéma* no 683 (review of *Augustine* by Alice Winocour)

The journey of *Fidélité/In-Fidelity* is a painful journey of jealousy, a continuous *crescendo* of what will become a crisis of hysteria that starts with signs such as incoherent speech and nervous laughs, growing gradually towards an explosion.

The image shows a musical score for a piano, specifically bar 197 from Georges Aperghis's *Fidélité* (1982). The score is written for a piano and features a dense, chaotic texture. It includes performance instructions such as "Joie sauvage", "5° sur le souffle", "stringendo", "Jouer avec frénésie, comme un enfant qui s'attaque à un jouet trop résistant. Prestissimo en produisant des sons comme si la harpe allait éclater. Laisser sonner certains sons, en étouffer d'autres.", "Pédales ad lib. - prestissimo - indépendantes du jeu des mains. Activité fébrile des pieds.", and "Arrêt subito". The score is marked with various dynamics and articulations, including a 20-second measure and a 6-second measure.

Example 2. Georges Aperghis, *Fidélité* (1982), self-published score, bar 197.

The association Anderson made between this explosion and the *petite mort* is not really convincing. Jealousy is not a pleasant feeling, the character is disturbed by it, and the climax is closer to a heartbreaking cry that becomes *joie sauvage* as a way of avoiding reality. That's why the explosion is followed by the character's suffocation; she/he can't breathe anymore, that's how painful the situation is. And after that, once she/he has lost her/his mind, she/he tells a joke that opens the end of the piece, which is written as a coda. This is highly disturbing and shows Aperghis's great dexterity in theatre and musical form. He had to find a way to end the work once the hysterical crisis has happened, when the despair of the character almost suffocates her/him. By telling a joke, the character has crossed the line of sanity, has lost contact with reality, and won't need to ask him

again (probably because he/she won't have the chance to): *so are you really happy to see me?*⁴²

The harpist does big cluster gestures with both hands while she's hitting the floor with her feet and keeps moving the pedals frenetically. The guitar is more limited and discrete in this sense, that's why Jude Anderson decided to commission sound artist Jacques Soddell to produce a short recorded passage of processed concrete and synthetic sounds to reinforce the hysterical climax of the piece, activated by the performer via a pedal actioned at the moment where the hysterical climax begins.

Aperghis puts on stage a harpist confronted by a very difficult virtuoso score as well as a difficult acting situation, that of having to recreate a hysterical journey during the fifteen minutes of the piece. The first cases identified with hysteria were displayed at the Salpêtrière Hospital in Paris by Dr. Jean-Martin Charcot in the late nineteenth century. His most famous patient, Augustine, became a star of those popular events, the "Leçons du Mardi," where Charcot and his assistants would hypnotise Augustine. She would have her crisis under the attentive eye of not only scientists but also intellectuals, thereby becoming one of the favourite subjects of gossip for *fin-de-siècle* Parisian society. Guy de Maupassant commented on the "Leçons du Mardi":

We all are hysterical, since Dr. Charcot, this high priest of hysteria, this breeder of chamber hysterical patients, looks after a crowd of nervous women in his onerous model establishment of Salpêtrière, inoculates them with madness and makes of them - in a short time - diabolical.⁴³

Hysteria is shown as a "*reflet dans un oeil d'homme*"⁴⁴ ("reflection in a man's eye") paraphrasing Nancy Huston's essay on twentieth century photography of women taken by men. Just like Aperghis and Charcot, and also Schoenberg with his Melodrama *Ertwartung* (which again features the figure of a hysterical

⁴² "alors tu es vraiment heureux de me voir?". Translation mine. Aperghis, *Fidélité*, p. 10.

⁴³ "Nous sommes tous des hystériques, depuis que le docteur Charcot, ce grand prêtre de l'hystérie, cet éleveur d'hystériques en chambre, entretient à grands frais dans son établissement modèle de la Salpêtrière un peuple de femmes nerveuses auxquelles il inocule la folie, et dont il fait, en peu de temps, des démoniaques."⁴³ Translation mine. Guy de Maupassant (signed Maufrigneuse), 'Une Femme', *Gil Blas*, 16/08/1882.

⁴⁴ Nancy Huston, *Reflets dans un oeil d'homme* (Arles: Actes Sud, 2012).

woman), it is always from a male perspective that an illness considered intrinsically female until the early twentieth century is showcased. In the inversion/adaptation *In-Fidelity*, hysteria is given a masculine dimension. Didi-Huberman points out that: “hysteria in the male is not as rare as is thought, and Charcot’s ‘polyclinics’ were filled with hysterical men, like the famous case of a man by the name of Pin. This was Charcot’s great act of ‘courage,’ his ‘discovery’ of masculine hysteria”.⁴⁵ Freud continued Charcot’s studies on male hysteria, presenting in 1886 a paper titled “On Male Hysteria” at the Imperial Society of Physicians of Vienna⁴⁶. Together with Joseph Breuer he published “Studies on Hysteria” (1895),⁴⁷ and although it describes no cases of male hysteria, the phenomenon is mentioned in its introduction.

An important aspect of this research is to prove that masculine hysteria can be explored as an artistic inspiration for Monodrama, just as female hysteria has inspired many male composers. Together with Corrales’ *BUG*, the study of a disturbed character will start with hysteria only to later evolve into trauma and other disorders in the works by Chisholm, Bongcam and Zea that will be discussed in the second part of this thesis.

⁴⁵ Georges Didi-Huberman, *Invention of Hysteria, Charcot and the Photographic Iconography of the Sapêtrière*, translated by Alisa Hartz (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2003), p. 80.

⁴⁶ As referred on Freud’s chronology on Laura Marcus (ed.), *Sigmund Freud’s the Interpretation of Dreams: New Interdisciplinary Essays* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1999), p. x.

⁴⁷ Sigmund Freud and Joseph Breuer, *Studies in Hysteria* (London: Penguin Books, 2004).

Part Two – Development of New Melodramas. Becoming the Embodied Acting Musician.

Preface

The second part of this thesis is divided in five sections, each of them studies a creation of a new work of Music Theatre:

-2.1. *BUG Trilogy* (2014), for guitar, violin, double bass, percussion and bass clarinet by Arturo Corrales, mise-en-scène by Christophe Bergon.

-2.2. *Egyptian Love Poem in Nihilist Cipher* (2014) for guitarist by James Rushford.

-2.3. *Intraluxxxel* (2015), Multimedia-Melodrama for Bb clarinet, e-guitar, two dancers, video and live electronics by Erick Bongcam, video by Alejandro Arango.

-2.4. *The Experiment* (2015), Musical Monodrama by David Chisholm, text by Mark Ravenhill, video by Emmanuel Bernardoux.

-2.5. *Kinecticut* (2012), Sound choreography for four performers and four computers (+ four Kinects) by Daniel Zea.

2.1. MALE HYSTERIA AND TRAUMA IN ARTURO CORRALES' *BUG*

"I don't deny the importance of text"

Jean-Luc Godard, from *Godard & Drug, Sympathy for the Devil*.

BUG Trilogy by Salvadoran/Swiss composer Arturo Corrales, a melodrama based on a key protagonist, is the first of the collaborative works of this folio that explore the possibilities of Monodrama as an "experimental product with whom the composer will look to renovate his/her dramatic language"⁴⁸. It "forms a cohesive twentieth-century tradition because composers perpetually designate it [monodrama] as a musical space reserved for the exhibition of female trauma"⁴⁹. The transcription and gender inversion in my adaptation of Georges Aperghis' *Fidélité* proved that it is possible to artistically explore hysteria *au masculin*. Therefore, working with composers on new works where the male performer could impersonate a disturbed character, suffering symptoms historically associated with women in the tradition of Monodrama, seemed appropriate.

Judith Butler's gender performativity theory proved to be particularly pertinent in the analysis of gender in both transcribed and original works:

"Gender is in no way a stable identity or locus of agency from which acts proceed; rather, it is an identity tenuously constituted in time –an identity instituted through a *stylized repetitions of acts*"⁵⁰. That repetition Butler points to is essential to her conception of how gender asserts itself: "Performativity cannot be understood outside of a process of iterability, a regularized and constrained

⁴⁸ "Produit expérimental avec lequel le compositeur aura cherché à renouveler son langage dramatique". Translation mine. Waeber, *En musique dans le texte. Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 411.

⁴⁹ Payette, *Seismographic screams: "Erwartung"'s reverberations through twentieth-century culture*, p. 31.

⁵⁰ Judith Butler, 'Performative Acts and Gender Constitution: An Essay in Phenomenology and Feminist Theory' (1997), in *Feminist Theory Reader: Local and Global Perspectives* (New York: Routledge, 2013), Carole R. McCann, Seung-kyung Kim (eds.), p.462.

repetition of norms.”⁵¹ . This iteration appeals directly to every classical trained musician, in that the constant repetition of technique and repertoire form part of the necessary routine to constitute a *sonic self*. When this iteration doesn’t take place a loss of aptitudes can be faced and existential questions can arise: what happens to the musician if those aptitudes are lost? Long breaks away from their instrument can be testing, and it can take weeks to rebuild a technique after a month’s break. At the same time, if we assume that by iteration Butler refers to a somewhat mechanic, repetitive and routine act that doesn’t leave much space for self-questioning, the act of stopping, even if it creates uncertainty for a musician - since their instrumental skills are not fully developed - can be beneficial in the reflective process. Writer Hervé Guibert reflects on the impact of this self-questioning moment on his diary: “It is in this ‘in between-two-works’ where I need to think that I don’t know how to write, that I don’t know anymore, that I will never know”⁵².

In a similar vein to Simone de Beauvoir’s statement that “one is not born, but rather becomes, a woman”⁵³, one could say, “one is not born, but rather becomes, a musician”. A link between genre and gender practitioner therefore can be established. Each musician learns his/her precise skills at the conservatory that will allow them to be compared with his/her peers, and if they are good enough, they will win competitions or enter an orchestra and eventually have a career. But what happens if the area they are interested in is not just musical, but intersects between music and another art form such as theatre, dance or a visual art? To apply Butler’s theory it suffices to interchange the terms gender and genre (which in many Latin languages are designated by the same word: *género*, *genre*, *genere*, *gênero*). Butler’s concept of *drag performance* is also applicable where “there is a ‘one’ who is prior to gender, a one who goes to the wardrobe of

⁵¹ Judith Butler, *Bodies that Matter: On the Discursive Limits of “sex”* (New York: Routledge, 1993), p.95.

⁵² “Cet entre-deux-travaux où j’ai besoin de penser que je ne sais pas écrire, que je ne sais plus, que je ne saurai plus”. Translation mine. Hervé Guibert, *Le mausolée des amants. Journal 1976-1991* (Paris: Gallimard, 2001), Collection Folio, p. 414.

⁵³ Simone de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex* (New York: Vintage Books, 1973), p. 301.

gender decides with deliberation which gender it will be today"⁵⁴. In the case of interdisciplinary performance, a *performative cluster* can occur when on one day one must be prepared to play hypercomplex music, on the next a complex score with dramatic elements as in the case of Aperghis, and on another an interdisciplinary project with a *mise-en-scène* and electronics where one must explore the performative maladies as neurosis as in the case of *BUG Trilogy*. It's no longer a question merely about the music; the abilities need to be broadened, the perceptions and critical awareness of the performer need to be awakened and expanded, and, if at the end of the process one needs to reflect in a paper or a thesis on the overall outcomes, then the intellectual aspects of the project intersect with the intuitive artistry. Far from the more compartmentalised educational framework of most musical institutions, practice-based research can liberate the researcher from labels and strict definitions and aims at a holistic vision of a complete artist. This aspiration that motivates my daily work is in direct opposition to Jacques Derrida's *Law of Genre* that opens with the emphatic statement: "Genres are not to be mixed. I will not mix genres. I repeat: genres are not to be mixed. I will not mix them"⁵⁵. Such a perfect statement should be completely and systematically disobeyed.

Scientists, scholars and psychoanalysts have agreed that hysteria was not an exclusively feminine trait, but could also appear in male patients traumatised by tragic events, such as during a war: "the hysteric questions the gender division that organises experience in the totalised concepts of 'male' and 'female', revealing the fundamental unfeasibility of confining identity to gender"⁵⁶. This universalisation of hysteria that underscored my adaptation of Aperghis' *Fidélité* also helped me commence a collaboration with composer Arturo Corrales with the image of a deranged neurotic guitarist as a starting point. In the space of three years, from 2006 to 2008, this collaboration resulted in the *BUG Trilogy*,

⁵⁴ Judith Butler, 'Critically Queer', *The Routledge Queer Studies Reader* (New York, Routledge, 2013), Donald E. Hall, Annamarie Jagose, Andrea Bebell and Susan Potter (eds.), p. 22.

⁵⁵ Jacques Derrida, *Acts of Literature* (New York: Routledge, 1992); Derek Attridge, ed., p. 223.

⁵⁶ Christina Wald, *Hysteria, Trauma and Melancholia: Performative Maladies in Contemporary Anglophone Drama* (New York: Palgrave MacMillan, 2007), p. 55.

which consists of three episodes: *BUG* for guitar and electronics; *Music Box* for guitar, violin, double bass and electronics; and *Re* for guitar, violin, double bass, oboe and percussion. The increasing presence of other performers in each of the sections of the trilogy heightens the sense of threat against the main persona: the alienated guitarist. His neurosis manifests as hysterical symptoms, similar to those described by Freud and Breuer in their “Studies on Hysteria”: clicks of the tongue, nervous breakdowns, unintelligible and incoherent speech⁵⁷.

tongue clicks

Example 1. Arturo Corrales, *BUG* (2006), cue 12-13, self-published score.

unintelligible speech: “je ne peuple peurle soes oemeuge”

Example 2. Arturo Corrales, *BUG* (2006), cue 5-6, self-published score.

incoherent speech: “Db: toc-toc-toc / Vln: oui / Db: il y a quelqu’un? / Vln: non / Db: c’est qui qui parle? / Vln: moi / Db: moi? / Vln: non / Db: quoi? / Vln: personne ne parle? / Db: c’est seulement une voix?”

⁵⁷ Many of Freud and Beuer’s patients share with *BUG*’s “patient” similar pathologies: “A more complicated method of conversion is revealed by Frau von N.’s tic-like movements, such as clicking with the tongue and stammering” (p. 67), “she accordingly answered me today without any further reflection but in great agitation and with spastic impediments to her speech” (p. 41), “...its relation to himself or to the main contents of his thoughts - and that is why it remained unintelligible” (p. 208). Freud and Breuer. *Studies in Hysteria*.

Example 3. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), cue 7-8, self-published score.

In order to obtain the necessary funds for a properly paid commission of the work, *BUG Trilogy* was composed over a period of three years. The three movements of this trilogy were composed and premiered as follows: 2006 for *BUG*, 2007 for *Music Box* and 2008 for *Re*. That was a coherent strategy to create a new work in three different stages taking into consideration the funding limitations that often constrain the commission of larger new works. The creative process from the first conversations between performer and composer until the first full presentation of *BUG Trilogy* at Festival les Athénéennes in Geneva happened over a period of eight years, from 2006 to 2014. That is not surprising, considering the long timeframes necessary to conceive ambitious projects, and similarly extended timeframes involved in the works by Bongcam and Chisholm that will be analysed later in this dissertation.

Even before starting the composition of the first of those three works, Corrales had a clear idea that he wanted to create a work based on the figure of the alienated guitarist as a protagonist. Beyond this, he was also interested in exploring the clichéd figure of the songwriter/performer who stands alone with his guitar or sometimes with a little band. Examples of this style of singer/songwriter abound in the Ibero-American popular/folk music contexts of the 1970's and 1980's. Their songs often had strong political connotations against the dictatorships that were dominating many of the countries of the continent at that time. They were usually censored and their live presentations forbidden by the different regimes: that's how songwriters such as Silvio Rodríguez became iconic figures in the Latin American popular music landscape. Nowadays this songwriter figure continues to exist in a post-modern era where

the political message is less present or completely absent. Singers such as José González took inspiration from those politically radicalised decades of music to produce a politically indifferent product sung in English instead of the former resistance songs sung in Spanish or Portuguese, depending on the singer's country of origin.

Inspired by this songwriter image, *BUG* just needs the guitarist, a microphone for the voice and a couple of cheap speakers to produce the "dirty" electronics reminiscent of the poor sound quality of many of the protest singers' concerts I attended during the Chilean dictatorship.

Like the songwriter who changes his repertoire from gig to gig, the works of the trilogy have the modular quality of being presented separately or as a whole. Even beyond that, the middle movement (*Music Box*) can also be performed in four different ways: as a solo guitar work, as a solo guitar work with electronics, as a trio for guitar, double bass and electronics, and finally as a quintet where the final instruments of the trilogy - bass clarinet and percussion - start to emerge by improvising towards the middle of the piece, and become fully present in its final movement *RE*.

Corrales' adaptable quality as a composer can also be observed when he had to change the instrumentation of his work: at the time he composed *RE*, Ensemble Vortex (which commissioned the work) included an oboist among its members. Since then the oboist has left the ensemble, and a bass clarinet/recorders performer became the new member. Corrales changed the instrumentation without really rewriting the part, that's why the word "oboe" still appears on the score.

Once the three works were created, the next step was to make of those three separated pieces an organic performance. This organic aspect was already present in the composition, by the use in *RE* of many of the materials already introduced in the previous movement. For instance in this example, Corrales takes the material from the second bar of *BUG's* K and he plays it again in *RE*, this time with the accompaniment of the rest of the instruments.

K

5/8 5/16 7/16 9 (2+3+4)/16 13/8

(surre ff)

L

6/16 7/16 6/16 8/16 6/16 4/16

rit tempo mp ff

Example 4. Arturo Corrales, *BUG* (2006), cue 43, self-published score.

5/16 7/16 9 (2+3+4)/16

hb

vi *legno tratto*
f vib. molto

cb

guit mp sf sf p

perc (subito) f

148 (ritmo lento) (chama) mp

6/16 rit. molto Tpo. (subito) 6/16 6/8

DU NEANT, UN MI

TOUT A L'EGARD

15

Example 5. Arturo Corrales, *RE* (2008), bars 145-156, self-published score.

Another example: at the end of *RE*, the violin plays the melody that serves as the material for Corrales' *Music Box*. It is quite simple, and Corrales twists it by using quarter tones and the bowing *col legno* in an extremely soft dynamic (*ppppp!*), resulting in a melody closer to a David Lynch soundtrack than to a typical music box melody.

Example 6. Arturo Corrales, *RE* (2008), cue 184 to the end, self-published score.

Corrales “reveals” the secret at the end of the work, which constitutes a very filmographic quality. In *Music Box*, the full motif is never presented in its totality, as in this example where the double bassist sings the first 14 notes a second lower:

Example 7. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), cue 29, self-published score.

At the opening of *Music Box*, the guitar also plays the first five notes of the melody a second lower, altering the first note for a F natural:

Example 8. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), beginning, self-published score.

The three consecutive quarter tones in the melody are used to build a repeated pattern on the guitar, this time a fourth lower:

Example 9. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), cue 17, self-published score.

Building *BUG Trilogy*

Corrales had previously met French director Christophe Bergon. After a couple of Skype meetings between the three main participants: composer, director and guitarist, and having assured the participation of the Ensemble Vortex in the project, a weeklong creative residency followed in 2014 at La Rochelle's Centre Intermondes. The subtle work of Bergon and his previous experience directing musicians in music theatre works by French/Polish composer Pierre Jodowski helped to produce the final work presented in festivals in Switzerland and Australia. Bergon accentuates the guitarist's isolation and solitude by confining him to turn in circles trapped by a barrier of music stands. That was also a great scenic solution to the really counterproductive theatrical issue of turning pages, so that everyone moves around the guitarist who is condemned to eternally turn in circles. Bergon also wanted to leave a stamp on the musicians' paths, so he decided to spread as many kilos of white flour as necessary to cover the floor

thickly. The musicians' steps superpose one to another leaving an imprint that brings to mind a palimpsest.

BUG trilogy, together with other works of the folio such as *The Experiment*, could be interpreted as an extension of "performance art", a term originally conceived to define an actor's or a dancer's solos, but which has been extended in the last decades "into the realm of music with an admixture of language and other vocalisations, the employment of a wide variety of nonverbal sounds, the use of audio and visual media to extend both the voice and physical presence of the performer, and a wide variety of instrumental, prerecorded, or electronic/computer accompaniments"⁵⁸. There are differences between the works of this dissertation and those done by "performers like Laurie Anderson, Pamela Z, Diamanda Galás, Kristin Norderval, and Maja Ratke [who] create their own large scale performance pieces, works in simple and direct or extended and exaggerated form, whose subject matter and principal characters are most often themselves".⁵⁹ These differences reside in the collaborative aspect of working with composers as a separate entity from the performer. The performer has the responsibility and rigour of curating the works he/she is participating in, with the creation of a coherent body of work an essential aspect of this research.

The term *bug* makes reference to pop culture, as the word bug is present in computers and films. The year of composition and premiere of the first movement of this trilogy, *BUG*, coincided with the launch of the independent film with the same name by the emblematic director William Friedkin⁶⁰. The main characters of both that film and this monodrama - Michael Shannon and myself - are essentially disturbed, the first suffering from paranoia and the second from neurosis. In computers, a software bug is an error that produces an incorrect result, and in its original definition, a bug is an insect. All these definitions of bug

⁵⁸ Eric Salzman and Thomas Desi, *The new music theatre: Seeing the Voice, Hearing the Body* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2008), p. 70.

⁵⁹ Ibid, p. 70.

⁶⁰ William Friedkin, *Bug*, (Film, DMK Mediafonds International, Inferno Distribution LLC, L.I.F.T Productions, 2006).

are embraced by Corrales in his work, with the idea of a “*bug* that, though harmless at first, proves to be progressively a destructive force that annihilates each action and movement”⁶¹.

In 2006 Corrales attended the Acanthes Centre’s workshop where he met Georges Aperghis. Influenced by Aperghis’ unique conception of music theatre, in that year Corrales composed *BUG*, with the idea of completing a trilogy during the following years. If Aperghis uses his own texts to build the theatricality of *Fidélité*, Corrales uses texts from a diverse set of authors, as well as his own: Jean-Luc Godard for *BUG*, Corrales’ own texts for *Music Box* and his own, Antoine de Saint-Exupéry and Blaise Pascal for *RE*. Corrales presents the texts as extracts, declarations of the absurd that fall into the absurd, using the word as a musical effect.

“‘Troubled strangeness’, is the profound and inalterable difference that provokes the melodramatic charm. The word finishes by sucking the blood out of the music (*vampiriser la musique*)”⁶². In *BUG Trilogy* the music is the vampire: it sucks the blood out of the words that, while more present in *BUG*, become less and less predominant in *Music Box* and *Re*. If words are predominantly associated with theatre, and sound with music, Instrumental Theatre refuses this predominance: “Music does not accompany theatrical actions, but it constitutes the theatrical action [...] all that is required is for that inherent theatricality to be lightened”⁶³. Under this prism, Corrales’ *BUG Trilogy* gets closer to this notion of theatricality proper – with parallels to Mauricio Kagel’s Instrumental Theatre – than to a notion of music accompanying words as occurs in a traditional theatre

⁶¹ “*Bug* qui, inoffensif au début, s’avère progressivement une force destructrice annihilant chaque action et mouvement”. Translation mine. Nemanja Radivojevic, ‘No Man’s Land’, *Dissonance Magazine*, vol. 127, September 2014, p. 54.

⁶² “‘Inquiétante étrangeté’, c’est la profonde et inalterable différence qui suscite le charme melodramatique. La parole fini para vampiriser la musique”. Translation mine. Waeber, *En musique dans le texte. Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 309.

⁶³ Björn Heile, ‘Mauricio Kagel’s ‘Instrumental Theatre’: Metaxis, Framing and Modes of Presentation – Five Propositions’, in *La Musique et la Scène. L’écriture Musicale et son Expression Scénique au XXème Siècle* (Paris: L’Harmattan, 2007), Giordano Ferrari (ed.), pp. 186-87.

situation. As one critic noted of the work: “The guitarist mutters about how words are lost to memory, but actions persist.”⁶⁴

Repetition in *BUG Trilogy* has little to do with the constant repetition of a pattern to create a certain mood in minimal music. Rather it relates to the obsessive, constant repetition of a short pattern that has an obstacle in front of it that prevents it from going further. The impulsion is there, the repetition happens because of a sudden block on the progress of the discourse. It is the effect of the bug that represents that human aspect of music, the mistakes that it generates give life and beauty to the music.

Music Box, the guitar repeats the pattern 4 times while the Db. and Vln. progress separately.

The image shows a musical score for three instruments: guitar, double bass (Db.), and violin (Vln.). The guitar part is the most prominent, featuring a sequence of rhythmic patterns with durations like (4+2), (3+4), (3+2+2), (3+4), (2+4), (3+3), and (2+4). It includes dynamic markings such as sf, sf, sf, and fff, and a 'cresc.' marking. The double bass part starts with a 'mf' dynamic and includes a 'rall. moltissimo' section with the instruction 'diminuendo poco a poco'. The violin part includes a 'rall. molto' section with the instruction '(peu a peu comme un robot)' and a 'cresc.' marking. The score is marked 'x4' at the end, indicating a four-measure repeat.

Example 10. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), cue 24-25, self-published score

The guitarist must speak and play a sequence of words and gestures that are designed to break down both semantic meaning in language and ideas of virtuosity and perfection in music. This critique of *new complexity* is evident when the performer is asked to play “errors”: sonic events that will be perceived as mistakes, yet are precisely composed in the extremely detailed fabric of the work.

⁶⁴ Matthew Lorenzon, ‘BIFEM: Vortex Ensemble, Bug’, *Partial Durations*, accessed December 10, 2014, <https://partialdurations.com/2014/09/16/bifem-vortex-ensemble-bug/>

RE, guitar cadenza

(178) entrée Hb.
CADENZA
lento, cantabile, fragile.

(179) cadenza guit.
+ G.C.

(180) Cordes à J = 40

pp — pp — sim.
* remplacer ad. lib., note blanche prédominante toujours,

progressivement →

♩ = 40

and. → Z → Z → Z

sempre rall.

progressivement →

♩ = 60, Plus veloce ogni volta

al niente — o — p — cresc. prog. — rit.

progressivement →

♩ = 60 rall. prog.

G.C. PPP

♩ = 60 stabile

PPP

19

(181) Cordes J = 30 (danzare)

ripetere con fantasia

progressivamente →

♩ = 30 (stabile)

(corta)

sempre rall.

progressivamente →

♩ = 30 (poco rall.)

(sempre accel.)

rit. poco rit. poco rit.

(sempre cresc.)

rit. molto

Wordblocks (répondent aux accents guit.)

G.C. continue J = 60

sim.

20

hb

vi sempre $\text{♩} = 30$

cb sempre rall.

guit

(cresc. molto)

perc

21 poco cresc. (colla chitarra) via G.C.

182 fff perc. 183 G.C. + Hb.

stop!

poco fizou sou P P P P P (pénale susceptible) une seule expiration jusqu'à la limite →

granulation (cra de l'archet écaué, contre les cordes)

p

mf

mf

p (chuchoté)

guit

mf

mf

p

perc

$\text{♩} = 60$ stable

G.C. P P P P P

22

Example 11. Arturo Corrales, *RE* (2008), cue 179-182, self-published score.

In this cadenza the motif starts very simply and increases gradually in complexity and tempo, with the adding of more and more “errors”. These include crossed notes that mean half pressure, imitating the sound of the mistake that happens regularly in guitar when a finger of the left hand doesn’t arrive at its fret at the right time, producing this almost percussive sound with no clear pitch. It constitutes a refined joke at the expense of *new complexity* and its many disciples and apostles around the world, some of whom espouse the attitudes expressed by scholar Frank Cox:

the performer has an absolute responsibility to perform all notes, all rhythms, all dynamics, etc., precisely as notated, and that an absolute one-to-one relationship between notation, responsible realization, and ideal perception is the only acceptable musical situation. Some degree of “human input” is generally allowed, but this may not overstep the strict (and for many, absolute) limits defined by responsible realization of the notated tasks.⁶⁵

It is impossible not to half smile reading such a statement. Being a performer of *new complexity* works myself, I’ve been able to see from the inside how new complex scores are prepared, rehearsed and finally performed, and how many arrangements and concessions are frequently done to reach a “correct” performance of the work. Finding solutions and simplifications of to accommodate what are often impossibly difficult scores is a common practice among *new complexity* performers.

With its rigidity and lack of theatricality and humour, the school of *new complexity* ended up triggering opposite responses in composers like Corrales. While the movement had an important influence in Europe and the United States (and even in Australia with ensembles like *Elision*), it has been slowly losing momentum in recent years. By trying to push instrumentalists’ capacities to the limit, *new complexity* “composers deliberately draw attention to the performer’s physical limitations by presenting a score that is physically so demanding as to be virtually impossible, leading to theatricality in performance, as well as the production of noises that are ambiguous “extraneous” to the score”⁶⁶. This somehow unwanted theatricality can be interpreted as a precursor of music theatre, in the same way that Robert Adlington sees the potential of instrumental extended techniques as a medium to highlight theatricality in music: “with extended instrumental and vocal techniques[;] the theatrical element of all musical performance was thus enhanced as a performer set about his or her

⁶⁵ Frank Cox, ‘Notes Toward a Performance Practice for Complex Music’, *New Music and Aesthetics in the 21st Century* (Hofheim: Wolke Verlags, 2002), p.80.

⁶⁶ Cumming, *The Sonic Self: Musical Subjectivity and Signification*, p.101.

instrument in ways that intruded upon and transgressed the ‘neutral’ codes of the concert ritual”.⁶⁷

Finally, the electronics in *BUG Trilogy* also constitute a comment on some of the institutions that elaborate a hyper-refined electronics language, and in this case Corrales makes a direct allusion to IRCAM. Even if Corrales uses their emblematic software MAX/MSP for his patches, he chooses a rather low-fi technology, privileging “dirty” sounds produced by cheap speakers to accentuate the idea of the bug. This choice is not only related to the means he had access to in order to produce the work, but was mostly a comment on how many works with live electronics privilege the electronic sounds in order to “hide” less interesting instrumental writing, or where the instrumental sounds are completely unrelated to the electronics score. As Naomi Cumming has pointed out: “A rounded, “expressive” sound (...) can be replaced by one that is harsh and guttural, spare and sparse, or electronically modified with a reverberance that is “uncanny” and disorienting, as if the “voice” remained without the normal limits of a embodiment”⁶⁸. Aggressive rhythmical passages or explosions interrupt this rounded sound, used by Corrales in many lyrical passages of *BUG Trilogy*, just as if the neurotic character of *BUG* suddenly reappeared in the remaining movements of the trilogy:

Music box: lyrical line interrupted abruptly by rhythmic elements

Example 12. Arturo Corrales, *Music Box* (2007), cue 14, self-published score

Also, the ‘rounded, “expressive” sound’ that Cumming alludes to and that is largely used by Corrales in his trilogy, is continuously accompanied, juxtaposed or interrupted by the rather low-fi, intentionally dirty electronics throughout the

⁶⁷ Adlington, ‘Music Theatre since the 1960’s’, p. 226-226.

⁶⁸ Cumming, *The Sonic Self: Musical Subjectivity and Signification*, p.204.

piece. This is highlighted by the inexpensive speakers the composer positions under the seat of the guitarist, as a distorted prolongation of his own, *dirtying* his *sonic self*: the bug is here more like to be a constant virus than an insect that can be easily killed. Finally it is not the words but the bug itself that “*vampirises*” the music; the *BUG* gobbles up the beauty, the lyricism and the complexity of this remarkable trilogy.

2.2. NEW MELODRAMATIC VOICES IN JAMES RUSHFORD'S *EGYPTIAN LOVE POEM IN NIHILIST CIPHER*

*Before this mouth smeared with ink,
A precious box filled
With adorable pearls, I cry out,*

*"What is this strange sign?
A talisman to avert the evil eye
From him we cherish . . .
Or a seal for the mouth of the jar
Enclosing the wine of pleasure?"*

Mouhammad al-Nawâdjî, from *To a handsome boy with ink-stained lips*.

Composed in 2014 thanks to an Arts Victoria grant I obtained to commission the work, two of the five movements of James Rushford's *Egyptian Love Poem in Nihilist Cipher* were premiered in 2015. The preliminary conversations with James considered the use of spoken word with music as a way of exploring contemporary Monodrama. After contemplating many possibilities of different texts, he decided to use "To A Handsome Boy With Ink-Stained Lips," a love poem by the fifteenth century Egyptian poet and mystic Muhammad al-Nawâdjî bin Hasan bin Ali bin Othman (1383-1455).

Nihilist Cipher is a cryptic system used by Russian Nihilists in order to organise terrorist attacks against the tsar during the late nineteenth century, a "method used by the Russian underground during the time of the czars. It was developed for use among prisoners. Most Russian prisoners at the time were kept in solitary confinement and forbidden from communicating with each other."⁶⁹ According to Sergey Stepniak, "the cipher was a protection if the police should conceive some special suspicion."⁷⁰ By choosing a queer love poem written in the fifteenth century by a Muslim poet and a cipher used in nineteenth-century

⁶⁹ Richard J. Spillman, *Classical and Contemporary Cryptology* (London: Pearson Education, 2005), p. 51.

⁷⁰ Sergey Stepniak, *The Career of a Nihilist* (London: Harper, 1889), p. 7.

Russia, Rushford makes a clear allusion to two highly queer-intolerant and repressive societies in the present day: Russia and the Muslim world.

For the first of the five movements of the work, Rushford dissects the words and restructures the poem as follows:

*“or out smear it in,
are soiled in or early out,
has this run in?
as is or heels feel new?”*

Rushford’s adaptation of the poem corresponds to a twenty-first century level of abstraction, an interpretation of al-Nawâdjî’s fifteenth-century art. His poetry, in the words of his French translator René R. Khawam, “invites us to play with words as well as the body. But the words themselves, shaped by the tongue, delivered by the lips, don’t they have a body of their own?”⁷¹ This is precisely what Rushford does, he gives their own body to the words of this queer love poem by coding them, giving them secrecy. The unintelligible sounds find their sense and their romantic mood through the conjunction of music and spoken word, highlighting Melodrama’s most remarkable characteristic. The choice of ciphering the poem to make it become secret is evocative of the centuries of repression the queer community has suffered and continues suffering, which contrasts with the freedom of speech in a fifteenth-century Muslim society that al-Nawâdjî’s poetry reflects.

“The ciphering was only occasional at first, the groups of large closely-written figures rising over the even lines of the ordinary handwriting like groves and bushes upon a field of grass”⁷². This observation by Stepniak offers a pertinent image that reflects my impressions performing Rushford’s piece, where the encoded writing system secretly emerges from the lush muffled music. Rushford

⁷¹ “s’invite enfin à jouer sur les mots non moins que sur les corps. Mais les mots eux-mêmes, façonnés par la langue, offerts par les lèvres, n’ont-ils pas un corps?” Translation mine, René R. Khawam, introduction to *La Prairie des Gazelles*, by Muhammad al-Nawâdjî (Paris: Phebus, 1989), p. 19.

⁷² Stepniak, *The Career of a Nihilist*, p. 7.

uses the Nihilistic Cipher to codify al-Nawâdji's love poem: the composer encrypts the text by using different techniques such as the Polybius square, plaintext and the use of keywords, arriving at seven different vocal effects:

- closed mouth hum
- closed mouth "S" (short)
- closed mouth "K"
- closed mouth "T"
- closed mouth tongue click
- open mouth "P" ("pop" sound)
- open mouth "P" with breathy exhalation

In a modern world where we use mobile phones and computers to transmit our most intimate thoughts through the internet - "we think we're whispering, but we're really broadcasting"⁷³ - the composer brings a rare secrecy to his music. Here, the complexity resides in the inscrutability of both the score and the resulting sound. In contrast to Corrales's response to the *new complexity* composition school, in Rushford the complexity resides in the hermeticism of the score. Corrales's intentionally notated "errors" and Rushford's inscrutability and "hidden" complexity are responses to a fashion in music where many scores start to sound quite the same, an impossible accumulation of incredibly difficult rhythms and intervals. However, "complexity (or form or structure or whatever) for complexity's sake is not the name of the game."⁷⁴ Instead of showing the performer's virtuosity, Rushford hides it, ciphers it.

If the text uses the nihilist cipher to encrypt the words, the musical notation is no less cryptic itself. As in Anton Webern's *Drei Lieder* for voice, clarinet and guitar op. 18, Rushford notates real sound instead of using traditional guitar notation

⁷³ Steven Levy, *Crypto* (London: Penguin Books, 2001), p.1.

⁷⁴ Leigh Landy, *Experimental Music Notebooks* (Chur: Harwood Academic Publishers GmbH, 1994), p. 98.

(which transposes up an octave). Also, instead of using the traditional one-stave notation, he chooses a keyboard notation on two staves. But what makes the decoding process extremely difficult is the use of scordatura:

Example 1. James Rushford, *Egyptian Poem in Nihilist Cipher* (2014), self-published score, 2014, p.2.

This extremely low register choice of scordatura, with the resulting low tension of the strings, frustrates almost any possibility for virtuosic writing. However, the music is quite difficult to execute, with a variety of extended techniques:

Example 2. James Rushford, *Egyptian Poem in Nihilist Cipher* (2014), self-published score, 2014, p.2.

For each of the movements expecting the epilogue, Rushford uses a different limited harmonic framework made up of relatively static and discrete chords. Then, in a quite baroque style he ornaments both voice and guitar with continuous trills, grace notes and arpeggiating chords:

Example 3. James Rushford, *Egyptian Poem in Nihilist Cipher* (2014), self-published score, 2014, p.3.

The composer builds a harmonic tissue with recurrent arpeggios and progressions, at times drawing inspiration from tonal usage.

The cryptic aspect of Rushford's music goes against a musician's normal way of

reading music. As Theodor Adorno has pointed out: “this language demands that it be imitated, not decoded. It is only in mimetic practice – which may, of course, be sublimated into unspoken imagination in the manner of reading to oneself - that music discloses itself, never to a consideration that interprets it independent of the act of execution.”⁷⁵ In the *Egyptian Love Poem* no mimesis is possible, as the score doesn’t immediately disclose itself in one’s imagination or on the instrument. Here every single note needs to be searched out, its position determined and, once the harmonic frame is clear, then the ornamentation and the extended techniques that alter most of the notes can be added. It is this extremely exhaustive work that represents reading this music.

But once the notes have been read and learned, then the miracle of Rushford’s music comes forth. Through an accumulation of guttural sounds accompanied by an extremely low scordatura that robs the instrument of its usual modes of colour and expression, Rushford creates a work that can indeed be expressive. In the same way that the utterly soft dynamics of voice and guitar are captured by microphones and revealed to the audience, the signifier of a ciphered poem accompanied by a spectral instrumentation in an unusually low register for the instrument notated in a cryptic style can reveal an expressive signified. The expression resides in being the decoder of the message, in being the composer’s chosen performer, the one who transmits his ciphered message. The signifier is not expressive in itself, but the signifier becomes so thanks to his/her performer. According to Adorno, “no music exists without expressive elements: in music even expressionlessness becomes an expression.”⁷⁶ From the performer’s perspective, it is essential to find those expressive aspects in the signifier, even the driest serial phrase has the potential to become a lyrical signified.

⁷⁵ Theodor Adorno, *Essays on Music* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2002), p. 115.

⁷⁶ *Ibid*, p. 117.

2.3. ILLNESS AND ITS METAPHORS IN ERICK BONGCAM'S *INTRALUXPIXEL*

*“and my guitar falls ill
string
by string”*

Mahmoud Darwish, from *The Butterfly's Burden*.

The process

Multimedia-Melodrama for Bb clarinet, e-guitar, two dancers, video and live electronics by Erick Bongcam, video by Alejandro Arango, *Intraluxpixel* was a project started in 2011 that had a final presentation at the Ensemble Vortex concert season on 5 February, 2016.

At the beginning of this project in 2011, Bongcam composed what corresponds to the final section of the work: the duo for clarinet, electric guitar and electronics. Following subsequent conversations with the composer, I started proposing the project to clarinetists interested in music theatre. To assure the visual aspect of *Intraluxpixel*, Bongcam contacted video artist Alejandro Arango. The three of us were finally able to meet in Mexico at the Centro Mexicano para la Música y las Artes Sonoras (CMMAS) in Morelia for a weeklong residency in 2014, where elements of the video and the *mise-en scène* started to take form.

The next step was to find an occasion to present the work in concert. The Ensemble Vortex assumed the production of the show, which was going to be directed by the composer himself. The space of a week and a half was allocated for rehearsal, but this raised a number of issues. The final presentation - in the unanimous opinion of all the members of the creative team - was a sort of sketch of what *Intraluxpixel* should have been. This demonstrates that a new music ensemble's administration doesn't necessarily have the experience or the budget to deal with the production of an interdisciplinary project. What is considered a normal rehearsal schedule for a new work is insufficient for a music theatre

work where music, dance, live electronics and video need to be brought together. New dance or theatre works have much more expansive time frames for development, that allow for reflection. In the case of *Intraluxpixel*, the typical of three rehearsals (each a three hour call), plus dress rehearsal and concert didn't work, even if it that was what the ensemble's administration considered viable in terms of budget. Unfortunately what happened with *Intraluxpixel* is an example of a work of potential that suffered from a lack of rehearsals. Many ideas could not be realised, such as the composer's desire that the final duo be played by heart. The option of improvising based on the written score wasn't realistic either, not because of the disposition of the performers, but because many elements of the production (including the live electronics and video) had to be triggered by specific musical moments.

The score

Intraluxpixel is structured in three acts. Even if all the characters of the work are present on stage throughout the whole work, the first act is about the examination of patient 1 (the clarinettist) by the nurses (dancers). The second act introduces patient 2 (the guitarist) in a wheelchair, who presents with a clear case of catatonia. It is only in the third act that both patients will interact, and this is the only musically notated part of the work. Bongcam introduces theatricality into the score, and all the musical actions correspond to some external aspect. For instance, musicians stop playing if their medication doesn't produce the desired effect anymore, and they restart playing only after the nurses give them their respective pills. As a composer who usually works in cinema, Bongcam understands music in similar terms to the early twentieth-century theorist of stage lighting and scenic design, Adolphe Appia:

Music is discovered to be closely linked not just to the word, but also to that part of the drama to which the scenic elements of production give visible form. It ought therefore to be possible to examine the expressive quality of music and consider how it relates to the *mise en scène*.⁷⁷

⁷⁷ Adolphe Appia, "Music and the art of theatre" cited in *Musicality in Theatre. Music as Model, Method and Metaphor in Theatre-Making* by David Roesner (London: Routledge, 2016), p. 30.

The score of *Intraluxpxel* opens with an *energico* that represents the patients' awakening, ready to play after the dancers/nurses have given them their medications:

Example 1. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 1-2.

This first agitated section is followed by a space for expressivity that allows the nurses to have a romantic moment between them. This interaction made the audience laugh, as the dancers hugged and embraced while trying to keep their balance dancing on their two-wheeled electric scooters:

Example 2. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 29-32.

Sustained chords on the e-guitar and multiphonics on the clarinet follow the virtuoso sections. These moments of lethargy are explained in part by the limited duration of the medication.

Example 3. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 53-65.

To reactivate the music, a nurse gives a pill to the clarinetist at bar 69 (the fermata is not indicated, it was decided during rehearsals). The medication takes effect and the musician/patient can again play a virtuoso passage:

Example 4. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 66-71.

A new section follows at a faster tempo, which is only possible after both patients ingest further medication:

Example 5. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 85-86.

Clarinet multiphonics are accompanied by e-guitar frenetic clusters produced by left and right-hand hammering on the strings:

Example 6. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* (2011), self-published score, bars 93-94.

This is the section in which the nurses start to attack the guitarist/patient by applying fresh “blood” all over his body, *contaminating* instruments and pedals. The guitarist stands with great difficulty from his wheelchair and in their last throes of death both musicians arrive at the end section of long multiphonics on the clarinet accompanied by occasional chords on the guitar:

Example 7. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpixel* (2011), self-published score, bars 128-142.

In the course of the musicians' demise, the nurses give the clarinetist a product that creates a foam emanating from the mouth, thereby simulating a final inconsolable gesture of agony.

This very clear dramaturgy in the music proved to be very helpful for the dancers to cue their movements, and it helped the musicians to bring the right theatricality to the music. Once the dramatic intentions of the score were explained, every gesture seemed very clear for everyone involved in the creative process. Unfortunately, not all those descriptions are specified in the score, making it very difficult to interpret the composer's intentions in his absence.

The frame

Intraluxpixel is a work about illness, inspired by the composer's own long traumatic stay in hospital. The voiceless performers rendered mute are a metaphor for the coma in which Bongcam remained for several weeks. As Susan Sontag has pointed out: "disease is what speaks through the body, a language for dramatizing the mental: a form of self-expression"⁷⁸. The patients - in this case the musicians - are confronted by the sadism of the nurses, dancers on two-wheeled electric scooters. The work had a musical antecedent in Franco Donatoni's opera buffa *Alfred, Alfred* (1995), "a twenty-five minute piece based

⁷⁸ Susan Sontag, *Illness as Metaphor and AIDS and its Metaphors* (London: Penguin Classics, 2009), p. 44.

on words overheard in a hospital in Melbourne, Australia, where he found himself in a diabetic coma in 1992.”⁷⁹ Bongcam’s *Intraluxπxel*, thirty-eight minutes of hospital nightmare souvenirs became (as with Donatoni’s opera) something comic, *buffo*. One of the contributions of musical melodrama or music theatre in treating trauma is that music serves the work by helping it become ironic and finally funny. This reaction is not always present in exploration of the subject by other theatrical genres or Performance/Live Art. The hurtful “seismographic screams”⁸⁰ present in Sarah Kane or Anthony Nielson’s plays or in performances by artists such as Franko B - evidence of this *mal de vivre* that even led Kane to commit suicide - find a humoristic reply in Donatoni and Bongcam’s works.

Trauma is “borne out of its ancient roots concerning physical attack, but equally from the notion of a resultant wound, which is now recognised as being either or both physical and psychic.”⁸¹ The wounded instrumentalists/patients in *Intraluxπxel* suffer both physical and psychic traumas. Both wear diapers underneath their hospital gowns, which has a comic effect as well as the distressing insinuation of the patients’ incapacity to control their own sphincters. The clarinettist endures the nurses’ medical examinations, they undress him and proceed to do their routine job.

⁷⁹ Salzman and Desi, *The New Music Theatre: Seeing the Voice, Hearing the Body*, p. 189.

⁸⁰ This term is from the title of Jessica Payette’s PhD dissertation, in which she analyses the influence and repercussions of Schoenberg’s *Erwartung* throughout the twentieth century: Payette, *Seismographic screams: “Erwartung”’s reverberations through twentieth-century culture*.

⁸¹ Patrick Duggan, *Trauma-Tragedy, Symptoms of Contemporary Performance* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2012), p. 15.

Image 1. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxxxel* Storyboard, Actos 1-2, own edition, 2014, p. 6.

The guitarist is more of a mental patient. His illness, catatonia, starts showing while one of the nurses pushes his wheelchair back and forward. At the same time he recites the names of medications interspersed with the words “healthy” and “happy” – the supposed effects of using benzodiazepines and other drugs.

PERSONAJES ACTO SEGUNDO

Image 2. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxxxel* Storyboard, Actos 1-2, own edition, 2014, p. 12.

The comic effect is created by the use of a high falsetto stuttered voice while reciting the names of medications, with the sudden relief in the voice that is provoked by the words “healthy” and “happy”. My character finds relief from his catatonic state only after having been given his medication. Only once he becomes “normal” can he play the guitar.

In Bongcam’s conception of the work it was fundamental that the dancers (Fabio Bergamaschi and Mariano Capona) felt uncomfortable while dancing. The composer’s first idea was to make them dance on roller skates:

Image 3. Erick Bongcam, *Intraluxpxel* Storyboard, Actos 1-2, own edition, 2014, p. 5.

An anecdotal aspect of a collaborative process is illustrated by how accidentally choices can be made. While watching the television show *Empire*, I saw a choreography for a R&B song in which the dancers were using the very fashionable two-wheeled electric scooters. I immediately thought of *Intraluxpxel*, and mentioned it to the composer, who adopted the idea. The dancers’

movements also look suspiciously similar to the way aliens move in Tim Burton's film *Mars Attacks!*

Silent Melodrama

While traditionally associated with the interaction between spoken word and music, Melodrama's flexibility as a term has seen it extended to forms in which words are almost absent or of secondary importance. According to Ben Singer, "Melodrama's nature as a cluster concept means that the genre's key constitutive factors can appear in any number of different configurations. One might have two completely distinct combinations – sharing none of the elements – yet both warranting the label melodrama."⁸² For instance, in silent film, Melodrama works on a nonverbal and emotional level, a "common base of feeling that crosses over all linguistic barriers."⁸³ Singer's definition of melodrama as a "cluster concept" is echoed by Jacqueline Waeber's concept of melodrama as an "*impure* genre because it mixes the musical with the non-musical [...], the melodrama makes the musical and the non-musical interact (which doesn't necessarily mean that they blend together)."⁸⁴ We can label *Intraluxpixel* as a melodrama, thanks perhaps to the inexactitude of the term, but also because of Emilio Sala's definition of it as "a genre in which dialogues leave space for the body to speak directly, and in which music's primary function is to make such bodies audible."⁸⁵ In Bongcam the dialogues are wordless, the dancers' bodies continuously dialogue with each other, as well as the instrumental dialogue in the final duo. When real words do appear, it is not to engage in a form of communication but to manifest the state of isolation and imprisonment in which the catatonic patient finds himself trapped.

⁸² Singer, *Melodrama and Modernity: Early Sensational Cinema and Its Contexts*, p. 54.

⁸³ John Belton, *American Cinema/American Culture* (New York: McGraw-Hill, 1994), p. 127.

⁸⁴ "Un genre *impur* car il mêle le musical au non musical [...], le mélodrame met en interaction le musical et le non musical (ce qui ne signifie pas nécessairement qu'ils soient en union)". Translation mine. Waeber, *En musique dans le texte. Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 14.

⁸⁵ Emilio Sala, 'L'opera senza canto: Il mélo romantico e l'invenzione della colonna sonora', cited in *Melodramatic Voices: Understanding Music Drama* by Sarah Hibberd (ed.), (Farnham: Ashgate, 2011), p. 6.

The presence of dance and video in *Intraluxpixel* traces a melodramatic tradition of the eloquence of the body or *eloquentia corporis*. This was already present in the first melodrama *Pygmalion*, which belonged to the eighteenth-century tradition of “speech based principally on the support of the vision.”⁸⁶ This interest in gesture is older than the melodramatic genre:

In Roman civilization the “eloquence of the body” (*eloquentia corporis*) commanded a great deal of attention. Two categories of professionals in particular, orators and actors, studied gesture intensively. Bodily gestures follow movements of the soul.⁸⁷

The poses of dancers acting like nurses trying to proceed to medical examinations, injecting blood into the patients and giving them overdoses of medications bring to mind a similar affectation in hybrid artistic expressions of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries such as the “tableau vivant” or “tableau scénique,” and the later “art of attitude”. As Gerda Taranow observes, “when a *tableau vivant* is struck, the actor becomes a scenic element, and his costumed attitudes contribute to his transformation into a figure.”⁸⁸ *Intraluxpixel* presents the handicapped trapped bodies of the musicians in dialectic contradiction with the eloquence of the dancers and video, as if in constant *delsartian* motion:

Delsartism [c.1880-1920] proposed a body that is both whole and fragmented at its joints, natural and part of modern technologies, available for modern dance choreography and projection on film screens.⁸⁹

Along with influences like inherited elements of Delsartism, *eloquentia corporis* and the art of attitude, *Intraluxpixel* includes references to the *Grand Guignol*, the *fin-du-siècle* Parisian theatre of horrors that remained popular until the mid-twentieth century. Its influence is evident in the aesthetics of gore used in the video, including flashes of surgical operations, torrents of blood, and the opening of the work with the composer’s own brain scan showed on the screen. At the

⁸⁶ “Discours fondé principalement sur le concours de la vision”. Translation mine. Waeber, *En musique dans le texte. Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 200.

⁸⁷ Maryanne Cline Horowitz, editor in chief, *New Dictionary of the History of Ideas* (Farmington Hills: Thomson Gale, 2005). Volume 3, Gesture, pp. 929-930.

⁸⁸ Gerda Taranow, *Sarah Bernhardt: The Art Within the Legend* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1972), p. 147.

⁸⁹ Carrie Preston, *Modernism’s Mythic Pose. Gender, Genre, Solo Performance* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2011), p. 59.

end of the piece the guitarist is attacked by the nurses who cover him in blood while the clarinettist foams at the mouth. This general taste for grotesque aesthetics throughout the work: musicians wearing oversized diapers and cadaveric make up, dancers wearing cheap wigs and having to keep balance in the acrobatics two-wheeled electric scooters, could insinuate an intention of making of *Intraluxixel* a popular show. It would be naïve though to assume that the composer conceived this Musical-Melodrama as a *grand public* spectacle, but rather as an ironic vision on the quite serious contemporary academic music theatre scene.

2.4. ERASING MEMORY AND TRAUMA IN MARK RAVENHILL AND DAVID CHISHOLM'S *THE EXPERIMENT*

"When a new work deliberately extends the possibilities of a tradition, [...] a further source for uncertainty is introduced in knowing the degree to which an inherited term is apposite."

Naomi Cumming, from *The Sonic Self: Musical Subjectivity and Signification*.

The Experiment deliberately tried to extend the possibilities of the tradition of Musical Monodrama, introducing a further source of uncertainty. This may explain why almost every reviewer of the work felt quite disoriented. The twelve reviews (which equated to the number of performances of the work during the 2015 Sydney, Adelaide and Melbourne Art Festivals) presented diverse opinions of the show, yet were almost unanimous in criticising Mark Ravenhill's text for its lack of coherent narrative. It was as if neither Hans-Thies Lehmann's classic text *Postdramatic Theatre* nor Samuel Beckett had ever existed.⁹⁰

As with Schoenberg's early twentieth-century Monodrama *Erwartung*, *The Experiment* "seeks to provide the audience with the opportunity to have a 'co-experience' with a protagonist."⁹¹ Unlike traditional opera or melodrama, here "the spectator is required to piece together a fragmented plot, or, in extreme cases, to construct one."⁹² This experience is one of an intricate narrative: "the linguistic and physical disjunction that is characteristic of modern monodramatic protagonists often makes this task a rather daunting one."⁹³

The almost unanimous request for a logical and linear narrative was far removed from what *The Experiment* presented to Australian audiences. For this work, a

⁹⁰ Hans-Thies Lehmann, *Postdramatic Theatre* (Hoboken: Taylor and Francis, 2006).

⁹¹ Jessica Payette, 'Dismembering "Expectations": The Modernization of Monodrama in *Fin-de-siècle* Theatrical Arts', in *Melodramatic Voices: Understanding Music Drama*, p. 139.

⁹² Emilio Sala, 'L'Opera senza Canto: Il mélo romantico e l'invenzione della colonna sonora', cited in Payette, *ibid*, p. 139.

⁹³ Payette, 'Dismembering "Expectations": The Modernization of Monodrama in *Fin-de-siècle* Theatrical Arts', p. 139.

multidisciplinary team formed by Mark Ravenhill (playwright), David Chisholm (composer), Mauricio Carrasco (performer), Jude Anderson (dramaturge), Emmanuel Bernardoux (painter and video artist) and Matthew Gingold (media artist), conceived “a challenging, demanding and at times ‘in your face’ performance.”⁹⁴

The term ‘in-yer-face’ has been used by journalist Aleks Sierz to designate a group of playwrights including Sarah Kane, Martin Crimp, Anthony Neilson and Ravenhill himself:

The widest definition of in-yer-face theatre is any drama that takes the audience by the scruff of the neck and shakes it until it gets the message. It is a theatre of sensation: it jolts both actors and spectators out of conventional responses, touching nerves and provoking alarm.⁹⁵

The sense of discomfort Ravenhill’s text produced in Australian critics was shared by their British colleagues some decades earlier: “unlike the type of theatre that allows us to sit back and contemplate what we see in detachment, the best in-yer-face theatre takes us on an emotional journey, getting under our skin.”⁹⁶ Strong images and strong language are an essential part of those plays: “I can’t piss. It’s just blood” is said by one of Sarah Kane’s characters in her play *Blasted*.⁹⁷

David Chisholm’s compositional inquiry explores the resurrection and reinterpretation of vestigial musical forms. These include his Oratorio-Requiem *Kursk* (2011) and a song book with baroque instruments *Parlour Tricks* (in development). After having manifested my interest in a long-form work for soloist with text, Chisholm started searching for a text to use in the composition of a Musical Monodrama. He saw a reading of *The Experiment* by Ravenhill

⁹⁴ Suzanne Sandow, “Review – The Experiment”, accessed April 12, 2016, <http://itsalmostimpossibletotell.blogspot.com.au/2015/11/review-experiment.html>

⁹⁵ Aleks Sierz, *In-Yer-Face Theatre: British Drama Today* (London: Faber and Faber, 2000), p. 4.

⁹⁶ Ibid, p. 4.

⁹⁷ Sarah Kane, “Blasted”, scene two, in *Complete Plays / Sarah Kane* (London: Methuen Drama, 2001), p. 34.

himself at the London Southwark Playhouse in 2009, just weeks after we had our first conversations about a collaboration. The composer and the playwright met and agreed to work on *The Experiment*. After multiple funding applications, residencies and developments the work was premiered at the Sydney Festival in 2015.

Chisholm's aforementioned interest in resurrecting vestigial forms shaped the way he structured *The Experiment*. In the first instance he was inspired by 1770 Jean-Jacques Rousseau and Horace Coignet's *Pygmalion* (1770), "that *Pygmalion*, with its half prose half music statue," in which the authors apply "a strict melodramatic alternation between text [...] and music."⁹⁸ In *The Experiment* the text is delivered in strict alternation with the instrumental interludes. The text passages are nevertheless not entirely free from music. Through the surround system complemented by a 48-speaker array created by media artist Matthew Gingold for the project, Chisholm used extracts from historical monodramas to construct a soundscape that 'accompanies' the text: "haunted, muffled extracts from *Enoch Arden* and the prologue to Britten's *The Turn of the Screw* are rendered unrecognizable, stretched and muted through extensive experimentations and editing in multiple software applications."⁹⁹

The structure

I. Preshow/Titles

After a preshow in which a rural homestead is projected onto an imperfectly aligned screen accompanied by radio voices disseminating news on the kidnapping of children, and fragments of the Q&A section of a Karlheinz Stockhausen lecture, the scene goes dark and the show begins.

⁹⁸ "Ce *Pygmalion* avec sa statue moitié prose moitié musique [,] monstre du génie de Rousseau". Galiani Abbot, *Gazette des spectacles*, 1773, quoted in Waeber, *En musique dans le texte*, p. 17; "applique strictement le principe d'alternance mélodramatique entre texte [...] et musique." Translation mine. Waeber, *En musique dans le texte Le mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 17.

⁹⁹ David Chisholm, "The Memory of Remembering, Exomologesis and Exagoreusis in *The Experiment*", in *The 21st Century Performance Reader*, Teresa Brayshaw and Noel Witts (eds.), (Abingdon: Routledge, 2018, in press).

II. Prologue

The first three minutes of the text are delivered in total darkness. Gradually a subtle light starts revealing the scene where is possible to see the performer surrounded by a microphone cage. This microphone cage was an allegory of the text and created the illusion that the voice was being captured and processed by them. In his review, Matthew Lorenzon stated that, “Seven microphones hang in a semicircle around Carrasco, capturing his voice from different angles and projected them, along with pre-recorded text, in a disjointed chorus.”¹⁰⁰ However, the voice was actually spatialised through the sound system by a DPA voice microphone discreetly positioned near the performer’s mouth. The illusion worked, giving the impression that the voices appeared randomly through one of the many speakers after being captured by one of the microphones that surrounded the performer.

Image 1. *The Experiment*, Jamie Williams

¹⁰⁰ Matthew Lorenzon, “Melbourne Festival: The Experiment” on *Partial Durations*, accessed April 16, 2016, <https://partialdurations.com/2015/10/24/melbourne-festival-the-experiment/>

III. Movement 1, 'We ran the tests on the children'

With the lights on, there is a projection of a slow morphing of red, pink and white viscera as “a conscious figuration of microscopic blood platelets and sperm,”¹⁰¹ which accompanies the performer during the first text section and the first guitar interlude.

Image 2. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

The performer recites the text seated surrounded by a microphone cage, then he moves to the spot where he will be performing the first interlude in a standing position. From the first conversations about *The Experiment*, Chisholm and I had agreed that it was important to invert the traditional stage set up, where the narrator is standing while the guitarist is seated. I remembered conversations with the Genevan luthier Jacques Vincenti, in which he mentioned the *tripedisono*, a pedestal invented and used by nineteenth-century composer and guitarist Dionisio Aguado to play the guitar in a standing position.

¹⁰¹ Chisholm, “The Memory of Remembering, Exomologesis and Exagoreusis in *The Experiment*.” (in press).

Image 3. Tripedisono. Tabazar – Geschichte der Gitarre, www.tabazar.de

A modern interpretation of Aguado's *tripedisono* was commissioned from scenic sculptor Nara Demasson.

Image 4. Own images

IV. Interlude # 1

The first interlude for acoustic guitar and fixed electronics is played on the instrument held by the *tripedisono*. It opens with harmonics that resonate on the electronics, followed by a tremolo in *accelerando* which bends half a tone at its fastest part and is echoed by the tape.

Example 1. David Chisholm, Interlude #1 for *The Experiment* (2011/15), self-published score, bars 1-4.

Example 1. David Chisholm, Interlude #1 for *The Experiment* (2011/15), self-published score, bars 1-4.

The very Spanish guitar *rasgueado* effect appears in four different moments during the piece and dissipates immediately afterwards. It is as if the act of remembering has faded away immediately after its appearance, as if ‘the memory of remembering’ – the title Chisholm gives to his article about *The Experiment* – was ephemeral and episodic. Just as Ravenhill reconstructs his memory after trauma by putting together pieces of the puzzle that quickly dissipate and continuously contradict each other throughout the text, Chisholm uses fragments of classical guitar clichés (such as the *rasgueado*) in his interlude.

Example 2. David Chisholm, Interlude #1 for *The Experiment* (2011/15), self-published score, bar 11.

Example 2. David Chisholm, Interlude #1 for *The Experiment* (2011/15), self-published score, bar 11.

A more agitated section constitutes the central part of Interlude # 1, giving it a rather classical A-B-A form, where B corresponds to the climax. Again ‘the memory of remembering’ also plays a role here, this time the memory gives a classical ternary structure to the Interlude:

Example 3. David Chisholm, Interlude #1 for *The Experiment* (2011/15), self-published score, bars 33-37.

V. Movement 2, 'Fairy Tale'

Once Interlude # 1 is finished, a video section follows. If the cues for the text were sonic in the first section, here they are all visual. The voice is processed live, with the only recorded text the very 'in-yer-face' word "cunt".

VI. Movement 3, 'The Room'

At minute 26 one of the screens is raised, creating depth for the performer to wander the stage and initiate the new section, in which he is in dialogue with a series of characters, who are represented by floating heads that appear randomly on the back and side screens.

Image 5. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

VII. Interlude # 2

After this 5-minute section the performer goes to the ‘incubator,’ which contains the e-guitar. A set of cameras have been placed inside the incubator to project close ups of the musician’s gestures.

Image 6. *The Experiment*, Shane Reid

This Interlude was commissioned from the Argentinean composer Fernando Garneró, and is a clear example of a long-term collaboration between composer and performer. I have had performed Garneró’s music since we were students at Geneva Conservatory. I have premiered the last four works that he has composed for e-guitar: *Ojo de Buey* (2013) for ensemble, *Limae Labor* (2014) for e-guitar and string trio, this Interlude (2014) for solo e-guitar and *Neon Pig* (2017) for

ensemble. In each of these works, the composer has used the e-guitar in a flat position, to be played over the lap, on a table, or, in the case of *The Experiment*, inside a cabinet where the guitar can be the subject of Garnero's 'experiment'. In this Interlude, the guitarist holds objects in both hands: a sponge and a slide on the left, a ruler on the right. The tablature specifies:

- the rhythm.
- the areas where the objects need to be placed. The placement of the objects in a specific spot of the guitar will determine the pitch.
- the direction in which the objects will move, indicated by arrows.
- the level of pressure of the objects over the strings, indicated by rectangles: white for light pressure, black and white for medium and black for hard pressure.
- the control of the wah pedal indicated by a circle for ON and a cross for OFF.

Example 4. Fernando Garnero, *Interlude* (2014), self-published score, bars 9-12.

Garnero, together with many composers of his generation who have been strongly influenced by Helmut Lachenmann's *musique concrète instrumentale*, uses specific nomenclature to denominate gestures, objects and extended techniques. That nomenclature is personal to each composer but it can also share certain elements, as is the case of Garnero with another Argentinean composer: Santiago Diez Fischer. The learning of new forms of notation can present challenges for the performer. I have found it useful to practise each of the elements separately, uniting them only after they have been practised individually. For instance in this Interlude, the correct coordination between the ruler in the right hand and the sponge or slide in the left hand is a first aspect. A rhythmic reading of their interaction, in the first instance, can be followed by the

correct application of pressure for each of the objects, and finally the addition of the wah pedal.

As is the case in Corrales' *BUG*, the repetition of elements has little to do with a minimalistic intention, but with an obsessive, constant repetition of a short pattern that has an obstacle in front of it that prevents it from going further.

This underlines Garneros' repetition of a 3/16 bar 21 times:

Example 5. Fernando Garneros, *Interlude* (2014), self-published score, bars 4-5.

Once the obstacle is overcome there may be a doubt about continuing, manifested by way of a seemingly lengthy seven-second fermata. Like a toy running out of batteries, the fermata become longer and longer by the end of the *Interlude*.

Example 6. Fernando Garneros, *Interlude* (2014), self-published score, bars 67-69.

The last fermata, the longest of the *Interlude* (eleven seconds pause), succeeds the last loop of the work, a seven times repeated 2/4 bar of a rising gesture in diminuendo that is produced by gradually closing the wah pedal. Is quite important to keep a 'frozen' attitude during this last fermata so the audience won't think that the work is already finished. A fragile last gesture in pianissimo finishes the work.

Example 7. Fernando Garnero, *Interlude* (2014), bars 71-72.

VIII. Movement 4, 'I forget'

The section that follows is about the performer proceeding to a self-examination with electrodes that he positions over his torso. Once he is fully cabled he places an archaic/futuristic helmet designed by Anna Cornick on his head. The helmet's light comes on, and the memory flashes of the patient/performer appear on the main screen.

Image 7. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

The whole text of this section consists of the performer's pre-recorded voice in a journalistic style, as if he were answering questions in an interview.

IX. The White Room (Interlude # 3)

A new interlude follows, this time for video and acousmatic electronics, and this is the only section of the work where the performer leaves the stage:

Image 8. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

X. Movement 5, 'Nothing lasts forever'

The performer reappears to deliver the monodrama's last spoken part, going back to the microphone cage of the opening, picking up one of the microphones to directly address the audience:

Image 9. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

XI. Epilogue, 'Galatea'

The last movement, *Galatea*, is a homage to the sculpture of the same name that *Pygmalion* brings to life in Rousseau's monodrama. It is a self-played guitar constituted by two different instruments joined together, as a Siamese twin guitar, which was built by Nara Demasson, with robotics by Benjamin Kolaitis. "The guitar is constructed from two guitars stuck together top-to-tail with a variety of solenoids and servo motors activating beautiful copper, brass, and wooden arms, plectrums, and wheels."¹⁰² The fact that for the closing of the work Chisholm decided to employ a robotic self-playing guitar while the performer stares at it quite perplexed, demonstrated that "the performer's body is not in a direct relation with the physical phenomenon of excitation/resonance anymore. It can even completely disappear from the scenic space."¹⁰³

Image 10. *The Experiment*, image from Vimeo

¹⁰² Lorenzon, "Melbourne Festival: The Experiment".

¹⁰³ "Le corps de l'interprète n'est plus en rapport direct avec le phénomène physique d'excitation/résonance. Il peut même disparaître complètement de l'espace scénique". Translation mine. Ferrari (ed.), *La Musique et la Scène. L'écriture Musicale et son Expression Artistique au XXème Siècle*, p. 123.

Textual undercurrents

The Experiment was inspired by Peter Singer's 1979 text *Practical Ethics*:

"If experiments are not prepared to use orphaned humans with severe and irreversible brain damage, their readiness to use nonhuman animals seems to discriminate on the basis of species alone."¹⁰⁴

This was the starting point for a monologue narrated by an undetermined persona about experimenting on children to find a cure for an incurable disease. It is unclear who the narrator is: it could be the partner, the neighbour, or one of the twins, or maybe all of them trying to remember the circumstances of a series of horrific experiments. The narrator constantly contradicts himself, as if he were trying to build the puzzle of his memories. While almost every reviewer tried to find answers to the ethical dilemmas of experimenting on children, nobody seemed to look at the metaphoric aspect of the work. In its simplest Aristotelian definition, "metaphor 'consists in giving the thing a name that belongs to something else.'"¹⁰⁵

It seems quite clear that a recurrent mention of the experimentation on children to find a cure to a previously incurable disease, that becomes manageable thanks to a pill a day, constitutes a metaphor for HIV: "'You are going to live my darling – and here's the first pill'. And I remember thinking that you were going to live forever."¹⁰⁶

Ravenhill's *Guardian* article "My near death period," earned the rather explicit subtitle "HIV, epilepsy, comas and memory loss haven't stopped Mark Ravenhill writing – in fact, they are what drive him."¹⁰⁷ This provides a clear clue to understanding *The Experiment's* metaphor: a generation that lived on the edge of dying from an illness could suddenly be partly saved thanks to a therapy consisting of a combination of drugs. Ravenhill's health was re-established but

¹⁰⁴ Peter Singer, *Practical Ethics*, 2nd edition (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1993), p. 58.

¹⁰⁵ Cited in Sontag, *Illness as Metaphor and AIDS and its Metaphors*, p. 93.

¹⁰⁶ Mark Ravenhill, "The Experiment", in *Plays: 3* (London: Bloomsbury, 2013), p. 437.

¹⁰⁷ Mark Ravenhill, "My Near Death Period", *Guardian*, 26 March 2008.

the consequences of AIDS-related diseases such as toxoplasmosis or the loss of memory of important parts of his life have remained with him.

This critics' tacit agreement not to mention the embarrassing subject - as if it was "highly desirable for a specific dreaded illness to come to seem ordinary"¹⁰⁸ - is explained by Ravenhill himself at the end of *The Experiment*:

"But as long as we don't talk about the experiments
We'll have a few years
And that's lovely."¹⁰⁹

While *The Experiment* mostly touches on issues of ethics and illness, there is an unexpected appearance of science fiction:

"Humanity has ended. Soon the last human will go
But that's alright
Because I'm going to make new humans
You see that's why I'm doing the experiments on you
So that when the time comes there'll be a new human race
And they'll all be made from your cells
If only I can get the experiment right
Do you see?"¹¹⁰

This is not completely surprising if we look at Ravenhill's later works, including the libretto for the opera *Elysium*, which involves trans-humans and human survivors and is set in 2118. Elements of horror and science fiction get into the mix with ethics to make of *The Experiment* a strange hybrid of genres:

"What if we're not humans
None of us are real humans anymore
But we're all just made by the man who cut at those boys in a shed in the..."¹¹¹

¹⁰⁸ Sontag, *Illness as Metaphor and AIDS and its Metaphors*, p. 180.

¹⁰⁹ Ravenhill, "The Experiment", p. 438.

¹¹⁰ Ibid, p. 435.

¹¹¹ Ibid, p. 438.

Monologue becoming Monodrama

Kagel's Instrumental Theatre and Chisholm's Monodrama share the quality of being "not synthetic but reconstructive."¹¹² The musical memory is gathered from the reconstruction and the further deconstruction of a tradition. Strauss and Britten's sound materials serve to create the sound landscape that will sustain the words: "Music does not accompany theatrical actions, but it constitutes the theatrical action."¹¹³ That's how everything in *The Experiment* is scored, the text fits the music, and the text *is* music since it becomes one with the acousmatic sounds: "In the music with fixed media, the tempo, the rubato and in more general terms the temporal scale are absolutely precise parameters in which the composer and the performer become one."¹¹⁴ Every gesture of *The Experiment* was rehearsed with the composer, every intonation of the text, every movement on the stage, every musical intention. Each show was presented in symbiosis with the composer, he was the responsible of triggering hundreds of sonic events that guided the performer throughout the work.

The Experiment also raises questions about the figure of the Acting Musician: "the work's spoken word is delivered in muted underplayed tones – and by a musician, not an actor."¹¹⁵ This points to a controversial issue¹¹⁵ in new music theatre, that of how trained in acting a musician needs to be. Clearly, all the works of the folio have been composed for a musician, a musician with interests outside the purely sonic world. A performer's interest in Monodrama and Music Theatre comes from the interdisciplinary, which I have been able to develop through collaborations with artists from other disciplines rather than through

¹¹² Björn Heile, 'Mauricio Kagel's "Instrumental Theatre": Metaxis, Framing and Modes of Presentation – Five Propositions,' in Ferrari (ed.), *La Musique et la Scène*, p. 184.

¹¹³ Björn Heile, *The Music of Mauricio Kagel*, (London: Routledge, 2016), p. 40.

¹¹⁴ "Dans la musique sur support, le tempo, le rubato et plus généralement l'échelle temporelle sont des paramètres absolument précis pour lesquels le compositeur et l'interprète ne font qu'un". Translation mine. Ferrari (ed.), *La Musique et la Scène*, p. 122.

¹¹⁵ David Chisholm, "The Experiment is a Musical Monodrama to Love, Hate or Both," in *The Conversation*, accessed July 10, 2016, <https://theconversation.com/the-experiment-is-a-musical-monodrama-to-love-hate-or-both-49137>

institutional training. Music education programs generally only provide acting training for more traditional stage genres such as opera and musical theatre:

“It is important to acknowledge that there are occasions when musical and acting skills can and indeed should be developed in isolation, actor-musicians require approaches to the breaking down and understanding of text, for example, and to physical and vocal flexibility and release as applied to the training of all actors.”¹¹⁶

However, *The Experiment* takes its cue from the origins of Monodrama, reflecting on the interaction of spoken text and music as conceived by Rousseau in his *Pygmalion*. Rousseau wrote that “cadence and sounds are born together with syllables: passion rouses all of the organs to speech, and adorns the voice with their full brilliance; thus verse, song, speech have a common origin.”¹¹⁷ Derrida reinterprets Rousseau two centuries later: “There is no music before language. Music is born of voice and not of sound. No prelinguistic sonority can, according to Rousseau, open the time of music.”¹¹⁸

This primitivism formed part of the conception of *The Experiment*, for which an unaffected voice was sought, to recite the text “in a careful monotone, trying to remember the circumstances of a series of horrific experiments.”¹¹⁹ *The Experiment* didn’t try to hide the performer’s lack of traditional acting training but sought to underline it, attempting to sublimate the words by simply speaking them and not performing them in a more theatrical way. As if it was trying to emulate Maurice Blanchot’s description of the moment where the word becomes Orphic:

“Then to speak is a glorious transparency. To speak is no longer to tell or to name. To speak is to celebrate, and to celebrate is to praise, to make of the word a pure radiant consumption which still speaks when there is no more to say, does not name what is nameless but welcomes it, invokes and glorifies it.”¹²⁰

¹¹⁶ Jeremy Harrison, *Actor-Musicianship* (London: Bloomsbury, 2016), p. 63.

¹¹⁷ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, ‘Essay on the Origin of Languages in which Something is said about Melody and Musical Imitation’, in *The Discourses and other early Political Writings* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997), p. 282.

¹¹⁸ Derrida, *Of Grammatology*, p. 195.

¹¹⁹ Lorenzon, “Melbourne Festival: The Experiment”.

¹²⁰ Blanchot, *The Space of Literature*, p. 158.

2.5. POST-APOCALYPTIC MELODRAMA IN DANIEL ZEA'S *KINECTICUT*

“Among the traits of the new subjectivity, in fact, was the loss of any active sense of history, either as hope or memory. The charged sense of the past – [...] – which had characterized modernism, was gone. At best, fading back into a perpetual present, retro-styles and images proliferated as surrogates of the temporal.”

Perry Anderson, from *The Origins of Postmodernity*.

Kinecticut, a sound choreography for four performers and four computers (+ 4 Kinects), by Colombian/Swiss composer Daniel Zea, was conceived in conversations between the composer and the violinist of the Ensemble Vortex, Rada Hadjikostova. She expressed her wish to play a work in which she wouldn't need her instrument. At the time, Zea was exploring ideas for a piece he had to write for the ensemble, a commission for a new work that celebrated Dadaism. The date of the premiere, 17 January, echoed Robert Filliou's 1963 declaration that art was first created on that day:

“It all started a 17th of January, one million years ago.
a man took a dry sponge and dropped it into a bucket full of water.
who that man was is not important.
he is dead, but art is alive.
I mean, let's keep names out of this.”¹²¹

Not exactly an artist related to Dada, Filliou belonged to *Fluxus*, a later movement that was strongly influenced by Dadaism. The Euroradio Ars Acustica Group's celebrations of Art's “Birthday” in 2012 - on what would have been its 1.000.039th birthday – were hosted by Swiss Radio, which broadcast two new works performed live by Vortex. Aside from the constraints of a live broadcast in terms of strict timing, creating new works live throughout Europe was an opportunity to manifest the Ensemble's adherence to some of the aesthetic and ideological principles of Dada and Fluxus.

These ideas gave Zea a base to work with, the materials with which he would later build his *Kinecticut*.

¹²¹ Anna Friz, *Traces of Art's Birthday network at the Western Front 1989 – 2007*, accessed July 28, 2017, http://www.artsbirthday.net/2007/essays/anna_friz_essay.html

Hadjikostova's idea of 'no instruments' was taken even further by the composer: since instruments weren't necessary, neither were clothes, nor lighting. The computer's screen became the only source of light, a screen that each performer carefully looks at throughout the work. The performers need to look at the screen to read the score, certainly, but also to see and follow how their bodies are scanned by the Kinect. This scan of the body determines the different parameters of the music: dynamics and textures.

The inexpensive and popular Xbox technology Kinect is used to play different games at home, from playing a match against one of the tennis icons such as Roger Federer or Rafael Nadal, to dancing in front of the screen following John Travolta's steps in *Saturday Night Fever*. In *Kinecticut*, the Kinect transfers the information to the computer MAX/MSP patch. The sound density of the oscillators and filters that make part of the sound synthesis are controlled by different parts of the body: for instance the movement of the pelvis controls the volume. The musical instrument becomes the body itself, the spatial distance between the body and the computer is indicated by colours that help the performer to navigate the score: red normally meaning "danger", while green shows a safer area. All that the performer needs to perform *Kinecticut* is contained on the screen: on each 'page' of the score the composer gives precise indications of which sound is aimed for, and indicates how the movement will influence the sound. The choice of sounds and the page turning are triggered by specific points in the space while the dynamics and colours of the sounds are executed by the distance between the body and the Kinect. This choreography is captured by an infrared camera that translates the spatial data into sound through a MAX/MSP patch designed by the composer and calibrated specially for each of the performers, depending on each one's height. The musical instrument is the body, and the sound is produced by the spatial distance between the body and the computer. The concept is like that of a Theremin, although the sound is triggered by the whole body and not only by one or both hands. *Kinecticut's* resulting sound universe is also reminiscent of the Theremin's sonorities, evoking the "postmodern retro-style of the perpetual present" mentioned by Anderson at the beginning of this section.

Image 1. *Kinecticut*. Image from the composer's website www.danielzea.org

Instead of using a traditional musical notation, Zea uses the Labanotation where the movement is notated vertically and not horizontally, the score is read from the bottom to the top of the screen:

Example 1. Daniel Zea, *Kinecticut* (2012), self-published score, p. 3.

In this type of work traditional musical notation presented clear obstacles and a more choreographic notation system was needed. In 1928 Rudolf Laban created the Labanotation or Kinetography Laban, that has been developed since by Ann Hutchinson:

The process of recording movement on paper involves the conversion of the elements of space, time, energy, and the parts of the body involved into symbols which can be read and converted into movement. When this process is understood, the logic behind the Laban system and the reason for the range of choice in movement description can be comprehended.¹²²

As *Kinecticut* forms part of a trilogy of works that explore body movement as generator of sound, our learning of Labanotation has been gradual since performing the first part of the triptych in 2012. Our knowledge and application of the symbols has developed over time, facilitating our engagement with the score.

Desplazados _ Lexique de notation (basé sur le système Laban)

<p>Les directions:</p> <p>en avant gauche en avant droite</p> <p>en diagonale avant gauche en diagonale avant droite</p> <p>à gauche en place à droite</p> <p>en diagonale arrière gauche en diagonale arrière droite</p> <p>en arrière gauche en arrière droite</p> <p>Les niveaux:</p> <p>niveau bas niveau moyen niveau haut </p>	<p>Les parties du corps:</p> <p> les bras (en entier)</p> <p> les épaules</p> <p> les coudes</p> <p> les poignets</p> <p> les mains</p> <p> les doigts</p> <p> le genou</p> <p> la cheville</p> <p> le pied</p> <p> la tête</p> <p> le torse</p> <p> le segment imaginaire entre la tête et le genou</p> <p>Les contacts:</p> <p> Les liaisons horizontales impliquent un contact entre les parties du corps. Ici le coude touche le genou.</p>	<p>Les extensions:</p> <p> grande</p> <p> petite</p> <p> très petite</p> <p>Les positions:</p> <p> en arrière en haut</p> <p> en place en haut</p> <p> en place en bas</p> <p> en place en diagonale gauche</p> <p> en place en diagonale droite</p> <p> en bas en diagonale gauche</p> <p> en bas en diagonale droite</p> <p>Les répétitions:</p> <p> répéter avec un rythme irrégulier</p> <p> répéter avec un rythme régulier</p>
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Example 2. Daniel Zea, *Desplazados* (2016), self-published score, p. 4.

Each of the four performers follows each of the scores at their own pace, having just one meeting point throughout the whole piece. However, as occurs with chamber music, each performer must listen carefully to the textures produced by the ensemble. That's why *Kinecticut* is a work for musicians and not for dancers.

¹²² Ann Hutchinson, *Labanotation: Or, Kinetography Laban: The System of Analyzing and Recording Movement* (New York, Routledge, 1991), p. 11.

In fact, Zea oversaw a performance by dancers, and while their bodies and movements were more graceful than the musicians, the musical result was not as refined and did not meet the composer's expectations.

Kinecticut is a work of music theatre, a sound choreography that can be described as Monodrama. According to Jessica Payette:

In the case of monodrama, [...], composers continually explore how music can enact visceral responses to different types of entrapment, ranging from those precipitated by ennui and violence. Needless to say, this is obviously a phenomenon that proliferates in the twentieth century due to the rapid dissemination of ideas resulting from advancements in information technology and recorded sound.¹²³

In *Kinecticut* each performer is entrapped in his/her own world. If the body moves too far away from a strictly delimited area the sound is no longer produced. The performers don't interact with each other on a physical level. *Kinecticut* is a work for automatons, in which the performers are together but alone, naked, in front of the only things that remain: a laptop, a Kinect, a speaker. They follow the screen instructions and scores, and when they get too close to the screen, synthetic voices announce fragments of quotations from philosophers and writers on our technological era and capitalist society. At that moment the performer pushes back and attentively listens to texts by Richard Kostelanetz, Georges Perec and Guy Debord. In *Kinecticut* the voice is used as an acousmatic voice, "as a foreign sound body, a non-musical perturbing agent used in a musical context."¹²⁴ This is a work about the vestiges of a civilization, a consequence of the twentieth century's rapid dissemination of ideas that went too far.

Kinecticut creates a post-apocalyptic impression. It is as if the only things rescued from the end of the world were a couple of speakers, some cheap games

¹²³ Payette, *Seismographic Screams: "Ertwartung"'s reverberations through twentieth-century culture*, p. 23.

¹²⁴ "Un corps sonore étranger reconnaissable entre tous, agent perturbateur non musical utilisé dans un contexte musical". Translation mine. Waeber, *En Musique dans le Texte. Le Mélodrame, de Rousseau à Schoenberg*, p. 284.

such as a Xbox Kinect, some laptops, and a bunch of post-humans who try to extract some sounds by using their own bodies. This returns us to Rousseau's idea of movement as a primary mode of communication:

Movement acts immediately through touch or mediately through gesture [...]. Thus only sight and hearing are left as the passive organs of language among men dispersed.

Although the language of gesture and that of the voice are equally natural, the first is easier and less dependent on conventions: for more objects strike our eyes than our ears, and shapes exhibit greater variety than do sounds; they are also more expressive and say more in less time"¹²⁵

In *Kinecticut* the gesture becomes expression, it creates the music, the movement creates the sound, the body is the sound. Language is said by non-humans, by synthetic voices reading extracts of what was once a thoughtful civilization. The post-humans, in a subjugated attitude, don't react or converse in reaction, but just push back and wait until the voice finishes its speech. For its original radio broadcast, a 'human voice' was used, that of the radio speaker reading texts from the aforementioned thinkers. However, since then *Kinecticut* has been performed several times and only the presence of the computer's synthetic voice has been privileged. This is a way of accentuating the expressiveness of gesture, a way of showing gesture as the most basic mode of communication possible.

¹²⁵ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *The Discourses and other early political writings*, edited and translated by Victor Gourevitch (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1997), p. 248.

CONCLUSION

Ceci n'est pas une conclusion

“In any reasonable drawing, a subscript such as ‘This is not a pipe’ is enough immediately to divorce the figure from itself, to isolate it from its space, and to set it floating – whether near or apart from itself, whether similar to or unlike itself, no one knows.”

Michel Foucault, from *This is not a Pipe*.

“I prefer to analyze melodrama as a ‘cluster concept,’ that is, to view melodrama as a term whose meaning varies from case to case in relation to different configurations of a range of basic features or constitutive factors.”

Ben Singer, from *Melodrama and Modernity: Early Sensational Cinema and Its Contexts*

This vision of Melodrama, or Monodrama, as a “cluster concept” can be linked to Foucault’s interpretation of Magritte’s famous work *Ceci n’est pas une pipe*, thanks to “the extra richness of language that allows us to say different things with a single word.”¹²⁶ That’s how Melodrama/Monodrama finds its manifestation in several arts, from the cinema and television to academic contemporary music.

If “of all performing arts, none has been more circumspect about its theatrical nature than classical concert music”¹²⁷, then music theatre, and more specifically

¹²⁶ Michel Foucault, *This is not a Pipe*, with illustrations and letters by René Magritte, translated and edited by James Harkness (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1983), p. 21.

¹²⁷ Adlington, ‘Music theatre since the 1960s’, p. 225.

Monodrama, goes against this tradition. As Robert Adlington has noted, “the theatre of musical performance was largely limited to a carefully circumscribed ritual of dress and behaviour; the performer who sought to assert his or her individuality over and above this ritual risked accusations of charlatanism.”¹²⁸ The theatricality of music is certainly an aspect that music institutions have neglected and continue to neglect, choosing instead a clear separation between disciplines. Therefore, the acquisition of acting skills by musicians who aspire to perform contemporary music theatre works happens in a rather autodidactic way. With the exception of a few music institutions,¹²⁹ most institutions train musicians as separately as possible from actors.

This educational impasse is partly resolved by the “Broadway” style musical theatre training, where actors access musical courses that will allow them to perform in musicals. The system invests in training actors and not musicians: “they [actor-musicians] also need space to develop discrete musical skills, such as ensemble music-making and the flexibility and technical command required to approach a variety of different musical styles.”¹³⁰ In the case of the Acting Musician presented in this folio, the focus should be inverted. The ‘discrete musical skills’ have already been acquired, while the acting skills should be encouraged and developed.

The musical education I received drew on “a romantic ideology that located musical content in sounds rather than actions or locations, [...] [which] came to ensure that the act of performance was, as far as possible, rendered invisible.”¹³¹ That is not encouraging for someone with a certain flair for other performing beyond music. Also, the educational system can quickly become quite

¹²⁸ Adlington, ‘Music theatre since the 1960s’, p. 225.

¹²⁹ The Bern University of the Arts in Switzerland, for example, offers a “Master of Arts in Théâtre Musical”.

¹³⁰ Harrison, *Actor-Musicianship*, p. 63.

¹³¹ Adlington, ‘Music theatre since the 1960s’, p. 225.

oppressive, especially considering the relatively poor repertoire that guitarists must play during their formative years. This often consists of an accumulation of pseudo folkloric pieces, which are privileged over more 'serious' works because of the supposedly popular nature of the instrument. It was beyond my institutional training that I discovered the 1950s avant-garde, which "became suffused with the spirit of theatre, first, because the virtuosity demanded of performers served to highlight the very act of performance."¹³² This discovery of Cathy Berberian and Severino Gazzelloni, among other performers, and of how they "transgressed the 'neutral' codes of the concert ritual" was crucial.¹³³ It revealed that other ways of being a musician were possible, thereby starting me on the slow path towards becoming an Acting Musician.

This folio presents a series of works that aim to prove that "music theatre tends to illuminate the awkward interstices between art forms, the gaps between existing aesthetic categories."¹³⁴ Through collaborations with composers, visual artists, media artists, dancers and theatre makers the vision of my own craft has changed, from a purely musical to a more interdisciplinary approach, where music encounters other arts, in particular theatre. Monodrama and the engagement with some of traditions and manifestations of melodrama have been the motors of this research. "Expressionism's thematic territory: breakdowns or incomprehensibility of communication and an individual's alienation in an increasingly irrational and threatening world" ¹³⁵ strongly influenced Monodrama in the first decades of twentieth century, and nearly a century later informed the works by Aperghis, Bongcam, Corrales, Chisholm, Rushford and Zea in this folio. Hysteria, trauma, melancholia and illness are explored throughout these works, and while the extent to which they employ words and theatrical elements varies, they can all be identified as Mono/Melodramas.

¹³² Adlington, 'Music theatre since the 1960s', p. 225.

¹³³ Ibid, p. 226.

¹³⁴ Ibid, p. 230.

¹³⁵ Payette, *Seismographic Screams: "Ertwartung"'s reverberations through twentieth-century culture*, p. 5.

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Appendix One.

Notes Towards a Performance Edition of the First Quire of *Platero y yo* for Narrator and Guitar, op. 190 by Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco.

Platero y yo, op. 190 was published as part of Angelo Gilardino's collection "Collezione di musiche per chitarra" by Berbèn Editions. Having compared this publication with the manuscript kept at the Library of Congress in Washington DC (Call number ML96. C34 no 172 Case Mario Castelnuovo-Tedesco) – accessible thanks to the composer's family authorisation –, it appears that Gilardino transcribed and typeset the manuscript without making any revisions or corrections. Therefore, an examination of the sources was necessary to facilitate the work's performance.

The first aspect to corroborate in a score that includes text is the alignment between text and music. The Bèrben edition consciously respects this alignment with the original text placed above the stave, and Eloïse Roach's English translation just below the Spanish text.

I. Platero

For this first movement a comparison was established between the Bèrben edition (hereafter BE), Castelnuovo-Tedesco's manuscript (hereafter CTM) and a revised manuscript version by Andrés Segovia (hereafter SM), which ignores the melodramatic aspect of the music and omits the text (this is also held in the same case at the Library of Congress archives). Whenever my version is different from the three mentioned above, I have included my proposed solution (hereafter MC).

With regards to the translation, it is exactly the same in the BE as in the CTM, except for the word "azabache" which is translated as "jet" in the first instance and "black" in CTM. Even if black corresponds to a more literal translation, jet

seems to be a better solution considering the sentence: “Sólo los espejos de azabache de sus ojos son duros cual dos escarabajos de cristal negro,” translated as “Only the jet mirrors of his eyes are hard like two black crystal scarabs.”

In terms of the music, the third beat in a bar of 4/4 is often presented as a crotchet in BE and in CTM, however the duration of a minim seems preferable, as indicated in SM.

Example 1:

BE, bar 4

CTM, bar 4

SM, bar 4

Example 2:

BE, bar 8

CTM, bar 8

SM, bar 8

The chord in the middle of bar 51 is impossible to play on the guitar. Segovia does well to ignore the duplication of the C in the chord using only the higher note.

Example 3:

BE, bar 51

CTM, bar 51

SM, bar 51

The passage *Un poco moderato (in 2)* from bar 52 to bar 63 presents the choice of keeping Castelnuovo-Tedesco's harmony. However, to do so it is necessary to cut the resonance of the chord, because of changes of position in the left hand. Another option would be to simplify the harmony by deleting certain notes that allow the left hand to stay in position. Writing chords and arpeggios for the

guitar always presents difficulties for composers. Collaboration between composer and guitarist helps to reconcile the compositional idea with its best instrumental translation, as is the case in the simplification proposed by Segovia.

Example 4:

BE, bars 52 to 61

Quando paso sobre él, los domingos, por las últimas
When on Sundays I ride him through the lanes in the

Un poco Moderato (in 2)

E. 1701 B.

callejas del pueblo, los hombres del campo, vestidos de limpio
outskirts of the town, slow-moving country-men, dressed in their Sunday clean,

y despaciosos, se quedan mirándolo:
watch him a while, speculatively:

-Tien'a se-ro...
"He is like steel," they say.

CTM, bars 52 to 63

Quando pass sobre él, los domingos, por las últimas colinas del pueblo,
When on Sundays I ride him through the lanes in the outskirts of the town,
los hombres del campo, vestidos de limpio y de paños, se quedan mirándole:
slow-moving countrymen, dressed in their Sunday clean, watch him a while, speculatively.

"Tiene se - er..." *Tiene se - er*
"He is like steel." They say *Steel, yes.*

SM, bars 52 to 63

(un poco moderato: in 2)

Finally, in the last section it is impossible to play the first chord and its repetition of the *chiaro e luminoso* from bar 66 without interrupting the resonance of the chord. Segovia proposes a very simple solution, just leaving the D, (the third of the Bm7 chord). However, I have opted to keep all the notes, by playing the 7th of the chord (A) as a natural harmonic.

Example 5:

BE, bars 66 and 67

CTM, bars 66 and 67

SM, bars 66 and 67

MC, bars 66 and 67

II. Angelus

For this second movement, a comparison has been established between BE, CTM and a composer's manuscript with added fingering by Segovia (hereafter CT/AS), who proposes some simplifications and articulations in trying to adapt the writing to the instrument.

In bar 5 Segovia simplifies a rather difficult G chord because of an impossible extension on the guitar. However, this chord could be kept if it were played as a slow *arpeggiato* (so that the 1st finger can play the bass G and have enough time to move towards the high D played by the 4th finger).

Example 6:

CTM, bar 5

CT/AS, bar 5

BE, bar 5 with my proposition

In bar 13 the resolution from the Abm chord to the G chord is interrupted if the notes of the second beat of the 2/4 bar are played as written. Two options are possible: Segovia's simplification (he omits the F) or trying to keep the dissonance of the second even for a brief moment playing the G one octave higher.

Example 7:

BE, bar 13

CTM, bar 13

CT/AS, bar 13

MC, bar 13

From bar 14 and throughout the section that follows, Segovia proposes a convenient articulation of slurs, as well as taking the bass E to the lower octave, which works well on the instrument.

Example 7:

BE, bars 14 to 24

a tempo ¿Sabes tú, quizás, de dónde
pp agnile, dolce e scriverale Do you perhaps know where all

es esta blanda flora, que yo no sé de dónde es,
rit. this tender flora comes from, for I myself do not know its source,

que entenece, cada día, el paisaje y lo deja dulcemente rosado,
mp cresc. which each day softens the landscape and leaves it sweetly rosy,

blanco y celeste — más rosas, más
p white, and blue — more roses, more

ro-sas—, como un cuadro de Fra Angélico, el que pintaba la
mf ro-ses—, like a painting by Fra Angelico, he who used to paint

gloria de rodillas?
mf cresc. glory on his knees?

CTM, bars 14 to 24

¡ahor tu, quisiera de onde es este flanda flora.
Doyra pasaba hono idese all de donde flora como foma.
que yo me se donde es, for I myself don't know its source.
que entrase, cada día al paraiso
y sedgia dulcemente con do, and less it sweetly say.
Kansy calaste, white and this.
mas rosas, mas ro-sas. como un cuadro de fanda
more roses, more roses. like a painting by fanda.
gchiso, gchiso. el que pintaba la gloria de rosasillas?
he who used to paint glory on his knees?

CT/AS, bars 13 to 23

In the *un poco più mosso* section starting in bar 25, Segovia simplifies the chords section by leaving a single slurred note on the last quaver of every two bars. This is a convenient solution for the instrument but not entirely necessary, as it is possible to play all the chords and maintain the complexity of the harmony.

Example 8:

BE, bars 25 and 26

CTM, bars 25 and 26

CT/AS, bars 25 and 26

Later in the section there is a very complex chord for the guitar, which is possible to play but requires preparation, which is incompatible with the *più mosso* spirit of the section. Segovia proposes to double the fundamental F instead of the third C#. I think that a better solution, given the rapidity of the section, would be not to double either note.

Example 9:

BE, bar 28

CTM, bar 28

CT/AS, bar 28

MC, bar 28

In the last two bars of *Angelus* it is impossible to sustain the Am chord while the notes of the triplets are played. Although Segovia proposes a solution by redistributing the Am chord, and neglects to play the final notes as harmonics, it is possible to conserve the chord as wished by the composer, as a simple triad, playing the notes of the triplets as harmonics one octave higher than written (plucked by the right hand), and to preserve the harmonics in the last bar.

Example 10:

BE, bars 58 and 59

CTM, bars 58 and 59

CT/AS, bars 58 and 59

MC, bars 58 and 59

III. Return

For the third of the six movements of this first volume of *Platero*, I had access to BE and CTM.

The editor's lack of rigor is evident at a number of points. The last chord of bars 25 and 26 is impossible to play on the guitar, without eliminating one note. Given

the voice leading it would make more sense to eliminate the E and keep the Gb as it is written.

Example 11:

BE, bars 25 and 26

CTM, bars 25 and 26

MC, bars 25 and 26

In the passage that follows the composer uses a parenthesis for a couple of chords, as he seems unsure about their realisation on the guitar. Gilardino reproduces the brackets without comment. There is no real solution other than that of creating the illusion that the chord lasts as long as possible after being plucked. One has to prioritise the lyricism of the melodic line, making the passage as *legato* as possible.

Example 12:

BE, bars 27 to 38

-ia la tarde de abril. *It was April dusk.* Todo lo que en el poniente había *Everything that in the west had been limpid*
p *p*
mf espr.
sido cristal de oro, era luego cristal de plata, una alego- *a smooth luminosity of*
gold was now limpid silver,
ria, lisa y luminosa, de azucenas de cristal. Después, el vasto *Then the vast*
Cape jessamine petals. *Molto calmo*
leg.
p dolcissimo

CTM, bars 28 to 37

bril. *dusk.* *mf espr.* *leg.* *p dolcissimo*

IV. Spring

In bar 73, the chord cannot be played as written. I have opted for dropping the C down an octave.

Example 13:

BE, bar 73

flores, por la *house - now*
mf

CTM, bar 73

MC, bar 73

V. The well

In bar 35 the editor forgets to indicate that the bass E is a flat, as it is in the rest of this passage in G minor.

Example 14:

BE, bars 34 to 45

vida a lo lejos. fied. ³⁵ Por el pozo se escapa el alma a lo hondo. The soul escapes to the depths through the well.

Se ve por él como el otro lado del crepúsculo. Y parece que va a sa- *animando* And it seems as though the

lir de su boca el gi- gante de la noche, due- ño de todos los se- *stringendo* giant of night, master of all the secrets of the world, were about to

cre- tos del mundo. *rit.* spring from the mouth of the well.

CTM, bars 34 to 45

The *largo e calmo* section starting at bar 46 provides further evidence of Gilardino's negligent work as editor. By directly transcribing a mistake from the manuscript, he has failed to substitute the last crotchet in bars 46–48 and 50–52 for a minim.

Example 15:

BE, bars 46 to 48

CTM, bars 46 to 48

MC, bars 46 to 48

Example 16:

BE, bars 50 to 52

CTM, bars 50 to 52

MC, bars 50 to 52

VI. Sparrows

Once again the composer's concerns about the feasibility of some passages is indicated by the use of parentheses. In the section from bar 21 it is better not to include the bracketed notes to enable greater fluidity at a fast tempo.

Example 17:

BE, bars 21 to 24

CTM, bars 21 to 24

From bar 25 it is not possible to play the ostinato G-F as written, and I have opted to play the G an octave higher.

Example 18:

BE, bars 25 and 26

CTM, bars 25 and 26

MC, bars 25 and 26

The *Lo stesso tempo* section from bar 43 needed substantial revision. It is not always possible to keep the bass line as written, or to play all of the chords as written by Castelnuovo-Tedesco. The proposed solution considers these aspects and the fluidity of a section that has to be played in a fast tempo.

Example 19:

BE, bars 43 to 60

CTM, bars 43 to 62

Lento tempo
mf *poco seleno*
Benditos pajaros,
 Blessed birds with no
 fixed holy day!
 Free in the momentary of the in-
 -stant, of the real,
 na - da a nos ser una
 holy man no - thing to
 usha vago, los dicen a el - los los cam -
 them sea - lon it be a vague journeyer.
 - fa - na. Con tentos, sin fatales obliga -
 Well content, with no fatal obli -
 - no force pin man

MC, bars 43 to 60

Lento tempo
mf *poco seleno*
Benditos pajaros,
 Blessed birds with no
 fixed holy day!
 Free in the momentary of the in-
 -stant, of the real,
 na - da a nos ser una
 holy man no - thing to
 usha vago, los dicen a el - los los cam -
 them sea - lon it be a vague journeyer.
 - fa - na. Con tentos, sin fatales obliga -
 Well content, with no fatal obli -
 - no force pin man

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In the *un poco più mosso* section beginning at bar 61 some simplification is necessary to enable the flow. I have omitted the E on the second beat of bar 63 and the A on the first chord of bar 68.

Example 20:

BE, bar 63

CTM, bar 63

MC, bar 63

BE, bar 68

CTM, bar 68

MC, bar 68

The *più vivo, mosso e festoso* section again demonstrates the composer's concerns via his use of parentheses. I have chosen to omit the E in bars 77 and 79, but not the B in bars 83 and 84.

Example 21:

BE, bars 75 to 84

- manos, mis dul - ces hermanos.
 brothers, my sweet brothers.
 Più vivo, mosso e festoso

CTM, bars 73 to 86

ral, son mis hermanos mis dul - ces hermanos.
 slow, they are my brothers, my sweet brothers.
 (a tempo)
 Viajan sin dinero y sin más
 they travel without money and without

The bracketed notes in bar 91 are playable but it is preferable to omit the third E of the chord in the bar to keep the continuity of this *vivo* section.

Example 22:

BE, bars 91 to 94

ntoja; presumen un ar - ro - yo, pre - sienten una
 strikes them; they know where to find a

CTM, bars 91 to 94

-toja; presumen un arroyo, presienten una
 strikes them; they know where to find a

MC, bars 91 to 94

- antoja; presumen un arroyo, presienten una

Finally, it is better to avoid the G in bar 125, as it is almost impossible to play the chord as written on the guitar.

Example 23:

BE, bar 125

un alegre e:
glad ex:

Musical notation for BE, bar 125. It shows a guitar chord with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The chord consists of a G4 note on the first string, a B4 note on the second string, and a D5 note on the third string. The bass line has a G3 note on the third string, a B2 note on the first string, and a D3 note on the second string.

CTM, bar 125

un alegre
glad ex
have

Musical notation for CTM, bar 125. It shows a guitar chord with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The chord consists of a G4 note on the first string, a B4 note on the second string, and a D5 note on the third string. The bass line has a G3 note on the third string, a B2 note on the first string, and a D3 note on the second string.

MC, bar 125

un alegre

Musical notation for MC, bar 125. It shows a guitar chord with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The chord consists of a G4 note on the first string, a B4 note on the second string, and a D5 note on the third string. The bass line has a G3 note on the third string, a B2 note on the first string, and a D3 note on the second string.

VII. Melancholy

For the last movement of this first volume of *Platero*, a comparison has been made between BE, CTM and CT/AS.

Segovia proposed some modifications to the manuscript: he takes out a totally playable A in bar 17 without much justification, and does the same with the F on the third crotchet of bar 24.

Example 24:

BE, bar 17

poco rit.

Musical notation for BE, bar 17. It shows a guitar chord with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The chord consists of a G4 note on the first string, a B4 note on the second string, and a D5 note on the third string. The bass line has a G3 note on the third string, a B2 note on the first string, and a D3 note on the second string.

CTM, bar 17

CT/AS, bar 17

BE, bar 24

CTM, bar 24

CT/AS bar 24

Segovia proposes an interesting solution to a passage which presents some issues for the guitar. The low F# in the second half of bar 26 as well as the G# and E in the second half of bar 27 are not possible to play on the instrument. Segovia redistributes the order of the chord and adds some extra notes that allow the bass line to keep its coherence, as well as maintaining the harmonic tissue of the section.

Example 25:

BE, bars 26 and 27

CTM, bars 26 and 27

CT/AS, bars 26 and 27

In a passage from bar 40, in which the melody is driven by the bass, he simplifies the passage by getting rid of the thirds in bars 42 and 46. While this is viable for the guitar, it is not totally justified, since it is possible to play the passage as it is written, keeping the richness of the harmony.

Example 26:

BE, bars 40 to 46

CTM, bars 40 to 47

CT/AS, bars 40 to 47

Finally in the section marked Tempo I in bar 55, Segovia's simplification can be avoided through the use of harmonics marked in an *arpeggio lento*.

Example 27:

BE, bars 55 to 62 with my proposition

CTM, bars 53 to 64

CT/AS, bars 53 to 64

¡Páese, amigo! - la dije y a la tierra "sí, como pienso, estás a-
hora en un punto del cielo, y llevo, robaste como paludo los
ángels adolescentes, jome balraí, quina, doudado

Tempo I^o
ad. - animo

p. *p.*

Am *Am*

CIX *CIX*

The image shows a handwritten musical score for guitar, covering bars 53 to 64. The score is written on three staves. The first staff contains the lyrics "¡Páese, amigo! - la dije y a la tierra 'sí, como pienso, estás a-" and the second staff contains "hora en un punto del cielo, y llevo, robaste como paludo los". The third staff contains "ángels adolescentes, jome balraí, quina, doudado". The score includes musical notation with various markings such as fingering (circled numbers 1-3), dynamics (p.), and articulation (accents). The tempo is marked "Tempo I^o ad. - animo". There are also some handwritten notes like "Am" and "CIX" on the staves.

Appendix Two.

Notes on the Adaptation of *Fidélité* by Georges Aperghis.

Linda Hutcheon builds each one of the chapters of *A Theory of Adaptation*¹³⁶ by asking the basic questions *what, who, why, how, where, and when* something should be adapted. I have used this framework to introduce the adaptation of *Fidélité* by Georges Aperghis (the score of which is presented in full at the end of Appendix 2).

What? *Fidélité pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme*. Second movement of a larger work *Compagnie – Tryptique n. 2* (1982). The first version of the adaptation was entitled: *Fidélité pour guitariste seul regardé par une femme* (2015, text in French). The second version was recast as: *In-Fidelity* (2016, text in English, translation mine).

Who? Composed by Georges Aperghis. Adapted by Mauricio Carrasco. Directed by Jude Anderson. Actress Sapidah Kian.

Why? The original work has a gender delimitation: *pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme* (for a solo female harpist watched by a man). In the interest of exploring this work as part of my research I opted to invert the genders as well as change the instruments. Therefore the work became: *pour un guitariste seul regardé par une femme* (for a solo male guitarist watched by a woman). Since the original production of my adaptation, I have performed *Fidélité* with men and women in the role of the actor, with the title recast as *Fidélité pour guitariste seul regardé par une femme ou par un homme*.

How? In the process of transcribing the instrumental part, there was an advantage in going from the harp to the guitar, instruments that have marked similarities. It wasn't necessary to transpose as such, but I had to tune the guitar's sixth string down to a low C to expand its register. The harp scordatura

¹³⁶ Linda Hutcheon, *A Theory of Adaptation* (New York: Routledge, 2006).

of an A# *désaccordée à l'extrême* (extremely out of tune) is replaced by bends on the A# on the guitar. Some chords needed to be reconfigured on the guitar to make them playable, and on occasion notes needed to be deleted. Finally it was necessary to find solutions to some instrumental aspects that were conceived more specifically with the harp in mind. These include:

- replacement of the ostinato of the pedal for a L.H. hammering between C and C#

harp original

guitar transcription

- replacement of the *glissando produit en tournant la cheville* by the use of a bottleneck on the L.H. that allows a microtonal glissando on the guitar.

harp original

A musical score in treble clef with a tempo marking of quarter note = 40 and the instruction '(parlé)'. The score consists of two systems. The first system has the lyrics 'pendant un instant, le regarde avec étonnement' and a musical staff with a dotted line above it. The second system has the lyrics 'si tu veux bon' and a musical staff with a five-finger glissando (marked '5') and a triplet (marked '3').

guitar transcription

A musical score in treble clef with a tempo marking of quarter note = 40 and the instruction '(parlé)'. The score consists of two systems. The first system has the lyrics 'pendant un instant, le regarde avec étonnement' and a musical staff with a dotted line above it. The second system has the lyrics 'si tu veux bon' and a musical staff with a bottleneck glissando (marked with a circled '4') and a triplet (marked '3').

- replacement of the *ongle le long de la corde* effect by a glissando in ricochet with the bottleneck on the R.H. over the strings 1 to 3.

harp original

guitar transcription

Where? When? These two questions appear in the same chapter of Hutcheon’s book, and they refer to the context in which the work will be presented: “An adaptation, like the work it adapts, is always framed in a context - a time and a place, a society and a culture; it does not exist in a vacuum. Fashions, not to mention value systems, are context-dependent”¹³⁷. For the object of this research, the English version *In-Fidelity* is documented, it was presented in March 2016 as part of the “Complete Smut art auction” during the Festival of Live Arts at the Arts House in Melbourne, Australia.

¹³⁷ Hutcheon, *A Theory of Adaptation*, p. 142.

Georges Aperghis

Fidélité

pour guitariste seul regardé par une femme ou un homme

adapted by Mauricio Carrasco (2015)

Original title:

Fidélité

pour harpiste seule regardée par un homme

From the beginning:

The spot where the guitarist will play must be intensely lit.

– Once –

A dignified woman/man enters the room, honourable, well dressed, holding the guitarist by his wrist.

Even the gaoler's gesture must be elegant.

She/he will release his wrist only once he has been seated – helped by her/him. She/he will go and sit a bit further away.

She/he will seem as if at she/he is listening and will stay inscrutable during the whole piece.

She/he will never look at him.

He starts.

Once he seems to have finished playing, she/he will wait to be sure, then will stand and will go close to him. She/he will help him stand, take his wrist and they will leave the room in the same way that they entered it.

Explanation of signs:

Guitar:

L.H. hammering between low C and C#

Ricochet with bottleneck's open end
over strings ① to ③ in glissando

Voice:

- ◇ breathe in
- ◆ breath out
- × speak

Fidélité

pour guitariste seul regardé par une femme ou un homme

Georges Aperghis

1982

Transcribed by Mauricio Carrasco (2015)

♩ = 92

Voice

Sion Sion (u o) toi you mout soft ible es ible as (lui her) dur hard

Guitar

♯ = C

3 rall. → ♩ = 40 rall. →

rien nothing non no

Do

8

il she toi mout you grinds ible ible es is lui her (dur hard) ça that

10 rall. → ♩ = 40 rall. →

rien nothing non no je fane à rieuse I fade to laughing

Do

15 $\text{♩} = 92$ *rall.*

mout soft ible is lui her dur ça hard that mé me cour yard

17 *rall.* $\text{♩} = 40$ *rall.* *(parlé)* $\text{♩} = 92$ $\text{♩} = 40$

rien nothing non no changeant brusquement de sujet: changing the subject abruptly: que je that I fane fade à in

20 *accel.* $\text{♩} = 40$ *accel.*

je I doute doubt fil thread fur rate fil thread fur rate

22 $\text{♩} = 60$ *accel.* $\text{♩} = 92$

fil thread fluite threat harpe guitar hier yesterday dis say a-vant be-fore

24 *rall.* $\text{♩} = 40$

à toi to you mi d'ou i half of or moi me prends take nuit yester-day d'hi-er night non not

26 $\text{♩} = 92$ *rall.* \longrightarrow *rall.* \longrightarrow $\text{♩} = 40$ *rall.* \longrightarrow

ible ible es lui dur ça mé (cour yard) non rien non

29 *H = expirations* $\text{♩} = 92$

H H H H il m'a H she had

33 *rall.* \longrightarrow $\text{♩} = 40$ *accel.* \longrightarrow

a- vant que je fane den se flu harpe fur
before that I fade den se flo guitar as

35 $\text{♩} = 40$ *accel.* \longrightarrow $\text{♩} = 60$ *accel.* \longrightarrow

la the jarre vase puis tien tière tierre sse sted lantes aint

37 $\text{♩} = 92$ *rall.* \longrightarrow

dis say hier yesterday à to a- vant be-fore ni d'ou i nuit night

39 *rall.* $\text{♩} = 40$

hier yesterday nuit d'hier yesterday's night es is

bend Do

43 $\text{♩} = 40$ (*parlé*)

soutient un moment son regard, puis se détournant avec un rire étrange, cassé
holds the look for a moment, then turns away with a strange, broken laugh

laisser résonner jusqu'à extinction complète

49 ($\text{♩} = 40$) *rall.* $\text{♩} = 40$

es is lui dur her hard ça that mé cour me yard rien nothing non not for deep

bend *bend*

52 *accel.* $\text{♩} = 40$

quel which mot word lui her moi me tant so

54 $\text{♩} = 60$ $\text{♩} = 92$ $\text{♩} = 40$ *sub.*

je then rou - gis I blush

58

j' fane I fade tant as much plor nos our clairs clear spaces spaces tant as much pleur cry

♩ = 60

63

noces nuptials clairs clear spaces spaces a-mants lo-vers rien nothing é-tions we-re H H H H H il m'a H she has

accel. presque chuchoté ♩ = 60

66

H mesH H brû-la mes mains mes poi-gnets H H H mes mains H my hands

H my H H burned my hands my wrists H H

♩ = 80 ♩ = 92

70

temps time le will di - ra H H tell

rall. ♩ = 40 ♩ = 92

72

♩ = 40

75 $\text{♩} = 80$

et sa voix H H mes mains H cueille moi es
and her voice H H my hands H pick me is

78 $\text{♩} = 60$

je for deep
I you— be dui zé com' si i' dev' et' vot'
I deep you— be have— as if I were yourpro-

80 $\text{♩} = 80$ $\text{♩} = 40$ (parlé)

prie té pendant un instant, le regarde avec étonnement si tu veux bon
per-ty y for an instant, holds look with amazement if you want good

84 $\text{♩} = 92$ $\text{♩} = 40$

a - mants rien clair noces
lo - vers nothing clear nuptials H H

86 $\text{♩} = 92$ rall. $\text{♩} = 40$ rall.

non t quo-ter je tif quel son (mot word) com
no you quo-te I son which word com such

88 *rall.*

rien nothing non no H H H H il m'a H she had

90 *accel.* $\bullet = 40$

H mes H H H brû-lant bur-ning mes my mains hands mes my poi-gnets wrists H H

92 $\bullet = 80$ *accel.*

H H mes my mains hands mains hands mains me H H

94 $\bullet = 92$ *rall.* $\bullet = 60$ $\bullet = 40$

for deep net poids mes mains mes las-se ti-red

98 *(parlé)* $\bullet = 60$ *accel.*

las-se de souf-frir of suffering tes mé-pris your con-tempt pas du tout ébranlée, gaiement hot at all shaken, gaily si tu ne m'aimes je if you don't love me I'd

103 *accel.* $\text{♩} = 80$ $\text{♩} = 40$

veux mou - rir / like to die n'ai - mes / love me tes mé - pris si tu / your contempt if you las - se / ti - red

107 $\text{♩} = 60$ $\text{♩} = 40$

v' vous cn' dui zé com' si i' dev' êt' vot' / you be - ha - ve as if I were your

110 $\text{♩} = 80$

et and sa voix her voice H H H cueille moi es / pick me is

112 $\text{♩} = 60$

je for deep v' vous cn' moi zé com' si i' dev' êt' vot' / I deep you be - ha - ve as if I were your

114 $\text{♩} = 92$

ray - on - nan - te rien non - ter quo / ra - di - ant nothing no te quo

116 *rall.* $\text{♩} = 40$ *rall.*

t te non no
ea eia
dur hard
lui her non no

118 $\text{♩} = 60$ *rire*

ray - on - nan - te
ra - di - ant
cueil - le
moi me
es je for
is I deep

120 *(rire)*

ray - on - nan - te
ra - di - ant

121

123 *(parlé)*

ray - on - nan - te
ra - di - ant

touchée, embarrassée par une
émotion dont elle n'a pas l'habitude
touched, embarrassed by an
emotion which she's unused to

125 (rire) ----- (rire) -----

a-lors tu es vraiment heu-reux de me voir?
so are you really happy to see me?

ray - on - nan - te
ra - di - ant

126

ray - on - nan - te
ra - di - ant

127

sou - dain elle se dé - tour - ne et vrai - ment a - vec em - pres - se -
su - dden - ly she turns a - way and re - a - lly ve - ry ea - ger -

128 (rire) ----- (chuchoté)

il lui lan-ce a-vec un sou-ri-re sé-duc-teur
she th-ro-ws a-t-him a se-ductive s-mile

a-lors tui es vrai-ment heu-reux de me voir?
so you are re - a - lly ha-ppy to see me?

dans un chu - chot - te - ment in - quiet trem - blan - te de peur mo - que - se et a - mu - sée frap - pée par ce mot
in an an - xi - ous whi - s - per trem - bling with mo - cking - fe - ar and a - mu - sin - gly struck by his word

(rire)

ray - on - nan - te sou-dain elle se dé-tour - ne et vrai - ment
 ra - di - ant su-dde - ly he turns a - way and re - a -

cresc.

a - vec em - pres - se - ment bran - dit son poing vers at lui é - mue
 lly ve - ry ea - ger - ly she shook her fist at him him mo - ved

mal gré elle et trou - blée par cette de - mande à peine dis - si - mu - lée a - vec un rire for - cé
 des - pite him and dis - turbed by this ques - tion ba - re - ly con - coc - ted with a for - ced laugh

bend

129 $\bullet = 80$
 (rire)

bend *bend*

131

2 3 1

♯bend

133

ray-on - nante sou-dain elle se dé-tour-ne et vrai-ment a-vec em-pres-se-ment bran-ditson poings vers lui A A A
ra-di - ant su-dden-ly he turns a-way and re - a - lly ve - ry ea-ger-ly sheshook her fist at him A A A

♩ = 60

fff

♩ = 120 con fuoco

134

(Râle)

fff

136

♯bend

138

♯bend

155 $\text{♩} = 40$ rall. \rightarrow

comme le mien / like mine / qu'au- cune rai - son / that no rea - son / ne m'o-bli- / re - qui - res

158 $\text{♩} = 72$ (rire) -----

geait à vous faire / me to make toyou / ray - on - nan-te / ra - di - ant

160

ray - on - nan-te sou-dain elle se dé-tour-ne et vrai-ment / ra - di - ant su-dden-ly returns a-wayand rea - lly

162 $\text{♩} = 92$

mes mains mes poi-gnets H H mes mains / my hands my wri-sts H H my hands

165 rall. $\text{♩} = 40$ rall. \rightarrow

sion sson t toi / t you / es quel lui mot / is which him word / dur hard com- / like

168 *accel.* \rightarrow $\bullet = 60$

oui
yes

un poi-son
a poi-son

173

o ni pour-rai- ja-mais si
or I would ne-ver could if

pas re-con-nais-sable
un-re-cog-ni-sable

175 *rall.* \rightarrow $\bullet = 40$ *accel.* \rightarrow $\bullet = 60$ *parlé chuchoté*

o
or

B.F. (nostalgique)

179 $\bullet = 120$

ni har-piemi-gnon-ne têt-te ni hon-neur har-pie ma têt-te ar-bo-ré hon-neur o ni pour-rai- ja-mais si gaie tu-er cro
not out-har py head nor ho-nour har-py gay my ar-bo-rescenthead ho-nour or nor nor e - ven could so gay not e-ven kill be

180 $\bullet = 120$

yez
lieve

bend bend bend

183 $\text{♩} = 120$
parlé
chuchoté

ni tu-er cro-yez si gai ni-er cro-yez ja-mais si gai je n'ai pour-rai ja-mais don-ner hon-neur o ni ja-mais tu-kill believe so gay de-ny bdieve so or nor e-ver could so gay nor I could ne - ver give ho - nor or nor could e - ver

er je or n'ai point don-né ni mon por-trait ni or har-pie mi-gnon - ne tê - te ni hon-neur har-pie ma kill or I have not gi-ven my por - trait nor yet e - ven cute my head nor ho-nour har - py head my ar - bo-

chanté normal

tê te ar bo ré hon neur o ni pour rais ja mais si gaie tu er cro yez je n'ai re - scent head nor ho - nour or I e - ver could so gay nor e - ven kill be-lieve I have

184 $(\text{♩} = 60)$

point don-né mon por-trait! not gi-ven my por-trait!

v' vous cn' dui zé' com' si j' dev et' vot' you be - ha - ve as if I we-re your

186 $\text{♩} = 40$ $\text{♩} = 120$

Do #

bend bend

189

H H H H

bend bend

191

$\text{♩} = 60$

sou - dain elle se dé - tour - ne et vrai - ment a - vec em - pres - se
su - dden - ly he turns a - way and re - a - lly ve - ry ea - ger -

192

ment ly (*rire*) ----- ne parle pas de ton coeur! ne parle pas de ton coeur c'est pure va-ni-té
ly don't talk a-bout your heart! don't talk a-bout your heart is pur va-ni-ty

a - vec em-pres-se ment bran-dit sonpoing vers lui A A
rea-ly ve - ry ea-gerly sheshookher fist at him A A

bend bend

193

u - ne bour - se de cuir rac - cor - ni s'ac - cor - de - rait bien mieux à ton vi - sage
a shri - ve - lled lea - ther pur - se wou - ld su - it you be - tter for a fa - ce

bend

194

(rire) 3

bend bend

196

Joie sauvage

bend fff (5" 7")

20"

Jouer avec frénésie, comme un enfant qui s'attaque à un jouet trop résistant. Prestissimo en produisant des sons comme si la guitare allait éclater. L.S. certains sons, en étouffer d'autres. **stringendo** (soudain pris d'une terreur subite d'être allé trop loin)

fff 6" Étouffer tout et rester figé à cette posture

rall. poco a poco (♩ = 40)

3 long long

(spasmes) garder l'air le plus longtemps possible

Activité fébrile des pieds

Activité fébrile des pieds

2/4 2/4

198 $\bullet = 40$ (mélancolique)

On demandait à un peintre pourquoi
il avait fait ses enfants si laids
Someone asked a painter why she
had conceived such ugly children

alors que ses figures
étaient si belles.
while her subjects
were so beautiful

205

Il répondit qu'il faisait
ses tableaux le jour
She replied that she
made her paintings by day

et ses enfants la nuit.
and her children by night

ni
neither

212 *se pencher lentement vers la guitare*

por - trait
por - trait

ni hon - neur
nor ho - nor

ma tête
my head

219 *calando* → *quasi niente*

o ni
o nor

si gai ni er ni
so gay de - nynor

ni pour-rai
nor cou-ld

o ni é cro-yez har
nor deny be-lieve har-

226 *il tient la guitare enlacée et sa tête en arrière*

pie ma têt' ar bo - ré hon - neur o ni
py my ar - bo re - scent head ho - nor o nor

La femme / l'homme attend pour
être sûr qu'il ne dira plus rien.
Puis elle / lui se lève, va vers lui,
lui prend le poignet, l'aide à
se lever et l'emmène avec lui.
Sévère mais avec élégance.
FIN